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GRAPHIA

Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for R&D in Social Sciences and Humanities

**Work Package WP2
SSH Knowledge Graph (KG)**

**Deliverable D2.2
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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ADR	Architecture Decision Record
API	Application Programming Interface
ARK	Archival Resource Key

ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
CIDOC-CRM	CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model
CiTO	Citation Typing Ontology
CLI	Command Line Interface
COAR	Confederation of Open Access Repositories
DACE	Data Aggregation and proCessing Engine
DAP	Data Acquisition Platform
DC	Dublin Core
DCMI	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative
DDC	Dewey Decimal Classification
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EAD	Encoded Archival Description
EDM	Europeana Data Model
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FOAF	Friend Of A Friend ontology
FRAPO	Funding, Research Administration and Projects Ontology
GPL	GNU General Public License
HA	High Availability
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
ID	Identifier
IMF	Internal Message Format
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
KG	Knowledge Graph
LCSH	Library of Congress Subject Headings
LPG	Labeled Property Graph
MARC	MAchine-Readable Cataloging
N2T	Name-to-Thing
NAAN	Name Assigning Authority Number
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OA	Web Annotation Data Model
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting

OCLC	Online Computer Library Center
OKD	Origin Community Distribution of Kubernetes
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PID	Persistent Identifier
POSI	Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure
PROV-O	PROV Ontology
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDF	RDF Schema
RiC-O	Records in Contexts Ontology
S3	Simple Storage Service
SAMOD	Simplified Agile Methodology for Ontology Development
SCHEMA	Schema.org vocabulary
SCRE	Semantic Content Retrieval Engine
SIOC	Semantically Interlinked Online Communities
SKG-IF	Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework
SKG-O	Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework Ontology
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOCro	SSHOC Reference Ontology
TTL	Terse RDF Triple Language (Turtle)
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VANN	VANN: A vocabulary for annotating vocabulary descriptions
XML	eXtensible Markup Language
XOAI	OAI-PMH Java Toolkit
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable, **GRAPHIA D2.2 – Technical Architecture**, presents the overall technical foundation of two GRAPHIA tasks, T2.2 (SSH KG Development and Deployment Infrastructure) and T2.3 (Data Acquisition Platform).

The document consolidates the main technical decisions made under **Work Package 2 (WP2)**, which focuses on the conceptualisation and implementation of the SSH Knowledge Graph. It describes the **semantic, architectural, and operational layers** that together form a coherent, FAIR-aligned and sustainable infrastructure.

The **first part** introduces the **SSH KG federation model**, which connects autonomous knowledge graphs through a shared interoperability framework, rather than relying on centralised ingestion. This federated approach ensures scalability, autonomy, and sustainability while maintaining global discoverability across participating graphs. The **GRAPHIA Ontology**, aligned with the **Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF)** and its reference ontology **SKG-O (SKG-IF Ontology)**, provides the semantic backbone enabling this federation. Its presentation is provided in deliverable D2.1¹.

The **second part** presents the initial design of the **Data Acquisition Platform (DAP)**, a modular, microservice-based pipeline designed to harvest, normalise, enrich, and publish data to both the GoTriple KG and GoTriple. It supports incremental and batch updates, operates under an eventual-consistency model, and enables efficient reuse of processing components across projects. The DAP embodies GRAPHIA's commitment to scalability, resilience, and maintainability.

The **third part** focuses on the **GoTriple Knowledge Graph (GoTriple KG)**, the main GRAPHIA-managed graph within the federation. It will be a companion service of the GoTriple platform that transforms its SSH metadata into a rich, machine-readable RDF representation. Beyond reproducing existing metadata (documents, projects, author's profiles), it integrates new categories of resources (datasets, media objects, semantic artefacts) and introduces AI-and NLP-based enrichment processes to extract entities and relations from texts, providing deeper and more fine-grained semantic descriptions of SSH data.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17951755>

This part also details the **technology stack and infrastructure** supporting the SSH KG.

The document also specifies the deployment model for the components described here, together with estimates of the sizing of the GoTriple KG. The persistent identifier strategy is also presented.

Together, all this outlines a coherent and sustainable technical architecture for the GRAPHIA ecosystem, forming a solid foundation for subsequent developments across the project.

2. Introduction

2.1. The SSH Knowledge Graph as a federation

The aim of the WP2 workpackage is the creation of the SSH Knowledge Graph (SSH KG). This work encompasses both the design of the GRAPHIA Ontology and the implementation of a federated infrastructure connecting multiple SSH knowledge graphs under a common interoperability layer.

The SSH KG is a quite vast concept, as it encompasses on the one hand the actual creation of a new KG, primarily based on GoTriple data sources, and on the other the federation with other KGs of the SSH domain.

The federation is in fact the only reasonable strategy to consider when large data repositories, with a high variability of changes, have to be integrated. Creating a single KG that imports data from all the other possible graphs and data sources will be difficult to manage from multiple viewpoints, including:

- huge amount of duplication that can be difficult to assess and manage;
- latency in data updates, generating inevitably stale data;
- high risk of creating references with entities that have been deleted or changed their IDs, resulting in wrong links impossible to solve;
- rigidity in adding a new graph to the federation, as this implies extending the data acquisition platform, possibly with new connectors to be developed from scratch;
- higher complexity and cost for the operation of the system, as inevitably a larger amount of data has to be managed;
- risk in including non-SSH-related content, as the other KGs might also cover different disciplines (think of OpenCitations).

These considerations motivated the project to adopt a federated architecture rather than a centralised ingestion model, ensuring sustainability, autonomy and cross-graph interoperability. This way, the SSH KG will be a federation of multiple KGs interlinked through the common interoperability layer defined through the GRAPHIA Ontology which has been designed around the Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) and its reference ontology SKG-O. Interoperability preserves cross-graph discovery and analytics, maintaining,

therefore, the global vision of a single point of discovery that hides the technical complexities of dynamically federating multiple graphs.

This approach significantly simplifies the technical and governance aspects of managing the graphs participating in the federation: organisations can manage their graphs according to their own governance, update cadence, schema, and operational rules. They can evolve independently and autonomously their data models. They must only adopt the common federation rules defined through the GRAPHIA Ontology, while keeping their local infrastructure and ingestion pipelines unchanged.

In this scenario, it is recommended that all possible data sources to be federated are actual KGs. Despite its name, GoTriple is not a graph-based system, and the term “triple” should not be interpreted as referring to RDF triples or semantic graph structures. The GoTriple data layer is in fact based on “simple” textual indexes, even if its data model has been formally described through an ontology. At the same time GoTriple is the main data source to consider for the creation of a federation of graphs around the SSH domain, being the largest SSH-only repository of scientific content.

All this mandates the creation of a new graph, the GoTriple Knowledge Graph (GoTriple KG), that participates in the SSH KG federation together with multidisciplinary KGs. Within this framework, the GoTriple KG represents the main SSH graph developed and maintained by GRAPHIA, designed to complement the existing GoTriple platform with a rich semantic layer. It provides a central access point for SSH data within the federation and facilitates semantic alignment and interoperability with other KGs through the GRAPHIA Ontology and the SKG-IF framework.

This does not imply any modification to GoTriple itself, but that the GoTriple KG will become a brand new service that complements GoTriple with the possibility to perform more sophisticated data analysis and, especially, with the availability of a way richer amount of data that GoTriple won't have in its indexes. As explained herein, this data will be created “ex novo” by analysing, via NLP and Artificial Intelligence techniques, the full text and the textual metadata of GoTriple's documents. Moreover, the datasets produced by WP3's tools and instruments will be also included in the graph. Therefore our intention for the GoTriple KG is to enhance

SSH textual metadata managed by GoTriple but also to create a significant amount of brand new data, not available elsewhere.

The overall architectural structure of the SSH Knowledge Graph is illustrated in Figure 2.1, showing the three main layers managed by GRAPHIA (ontology, interoperability, and data federation).

The ontology layer provides the semantic backbone aligned with SKG-O, the interoperability layer (based on SKG-IF) connects autonomous graphs through standardised APIs and alignment modules, and the federation layer integrates both the GRAPHIA-managed GoTriple KG and external SSH knowledge graphs.

* Future integrations: The federation will expand to include E-RIHS DIGILAB, Matilda, ReReSearch, and other domain-specific graphs.

Figure 2.1 – Federated architecture of the SSH Knowledge Graph (GRAPHIA SSH KG)

The SSH KG is structured in three layers:

- (1) the Ontology Layer, defining the semantic model (GRAPHIA Ontology aligned with SKG-O);
- (2) the Interoperability Layer, including standard APIs and mappings based on SKG-IF and enabling cross-graph alignment and discovery;

(3) the Federated Knowledge Graphs, including the GoTriple KG (managed by GRAPHIA) and external SSH KGs (e.g. EHRI, GESIS, OpenCitations, ORKG).

The architecture is designed to scale beyond the initial core partners (OpenCitations, ORKG, GESIS). It will support the federation of the broader ecosystem of domain-specific graphs defined in the Grant Agreement, including Matilda (bibliometrics), ReIReSearch (Religious studies), and E-RIHS DIGILAB (Heritage Science), paving the way for further integrations as the ecosystem expands.

2.2. Purpose and Scope of the Document

As indicated above, the implementation of the SSH KG will center on:

- the creation of the federation rules, via the GRAPHIA ontology
- the actual implementation of a new SSH graph, the GoTriple KG.

As the former aspect is taken into consideration in the GRAPHIA Ontology, presented in the GRAPHIA deliverable D2.1, released at the same time of this document, we do not take it into consideration in the present deliverable, which will be focused only on the second point.

For the implementation of the GoTriple KG we have to take into account three main aspects:

- the **Data Model** to formally describe the data of the graph, which will be an extension of the GoTriple.eu discovery platform, including therefore, in an expressive graph form, all metadata managed through it.
- the creation of an efficient, scalable, and reliable **Data Acquisition Platform**. The platform should integrate a flexible processing model, in which each curation and enrichment service is implemented as an autonomous microservice, with minimal dependencies with the others. Also, the update of the information in the graph must embrace the “eventual consistency” approach, meaning that updates propagated from different sources are not required to be immediately synchronized, but are instead progressively aligned over time to guarantee scalability, robustness, and tolerance to temporary inconsistencies. This way we avoid the risk of creating blocking points in the processing and the overall logic will be free of any critical path. When fully

operational, this platform can feed both the GoTriple KG and GoTriple's indexes, to save overall processing time.

- the actual implementation of the **GoTriple KG**, in a way that can ensure both the maximum expressivity and a rigorous management of its data. To reach this goal, it has been decided to use an RDF Triple Store. At same time, to implement advanced data processing and visualisation on graph data, a sophisticated LPG-based graph will be also included, to better support the modern needs of Digital Humanists and Data Scientists.

2.3. Structure of the Document

This document is organised by taking into consideration the main points described above. Therefore Section 3 presents the proposal for the GoTriple KG Data Model, that is based on the previous work done for the ontology used in GoTriple (the TRIPLE Ontology). Also, specific extensions are presented to take into account the brand new data that the GoTriple KG must manage beyond the metadata already included in GoTriple.

Section 4 presents the design of the Data Acquisition Platform, with its requirements and the implementation decisions that have been chosen.

Section 5 introduces the technology chosen for implementing the GoTriple KG. The decision process that led to the final choice of combining an RDF Triple Store with an LPG-based graph is also explained in full.

An initial development roadmap is presented in section 6, while the conclusions in section 7 present a concise summary of the work done so far in tasks T2.2 and T2.3.

3. The GoTriple KG Data Model

3.1. Introducing GoTriple.eu

As said in the introduction, in WP2 we aim to turn GoTriple data into a graph. GoTriple² is a multilingual discovery platform for the Social Sciences and Humanities. It is the main outcome of the TRIPLE research project, which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation action (funding scheme INFRAEOSC-02-2019 "Prototyping new innovative services"). The project, whose full name is "Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration", ran between October 2019 and March 2023: it was coordinated by CNRS and featured 22 partners from 15 different European countries.

Currently there are other research projects that extend GoTriple from different viewpoints: GRAPHIA, as this document presents, aims at creating the GoTriple KG, which is a sort of "companion" service for GoTriple.

The work in ATRIUM³ allowed to extend and improve the TRIPLE ontology, especially to better align it with other notable vocabularies of the SSH domain. In ATRIUM specific extensions of GoTriple have been also implemented, including the development of new data connectors, improvements of the platform's APIs, or the integration with the services of other European research infrastructures.

FASCA⁴ is creating AI-based tools and services for digital humanists and data scientists integrated in GoTriple: this allows an important reuse of GoTriple data, a reuse that the results of GRAPHIA will only but improve.

Finally, LUMEN⁵ is working on the one hand on enriching GoTriple with new advanced functionalities (AI chatbots, visualizations,...) and on the other on generalising the platform to become a "White Label" software that any scientific community can use to implement its own discovery platform.

² <https://gotriple.eu>

³ <https://atrium-research.eu/>

⁴

<https://oscars-project.eu/projects/fasca-facilitating-scholarly-communication-analysis-through-gotriple-pipeline>

⁵ <https://lumenproject.eu/>

From a functional viewpoint, GoTriple provides a central access point that allows users to explore, find, access and reuse materials such as articles, datasets, project descriptions and authors profiles at European scale.

It is one of the Discovery Services of OPERAS, the Research Infrastructure that supports open scholarly communication in the Social Sciences and Humanities in the European Research Area.

At its heart GoTriple has a search engine whose indexes are fed by a configurable harvesting and processing pipeline, that continuously imports and processes publications and projects metadata from multiple sources (over 1,500), including large aggregators (BASE, DOAJ, OpenAire, Isidore) and national repositories alike (Hrčak, Biblioteka Nauki, ZRC Sazu, EKT, Recyt, DNB or Pombaline).

Finally, users can register to the platform to create a personal profile, to claim the ownership of the documents published in the indexes, and to find and connect with other SSH authors and researchers.

At the time of writing GoTriple.eu contains the descriptions of about 20 million documents, over 26 thousand projects and of over 18 million authors. It is important to consider that “document” in GoTriple is an “umbrella” term that includes a rich variety of content types. Figure 3.1, showing in percentage the presence of the different types of objects in the documents index, gives an idea of this variety.

Figure 3.1 – Distribution of typologies of GoTriple documents

While the vast majority of documents correspond to textual material (articles, text, thesis, conference papers, reports, books, book parts, etc.) there is a certain amount of content of a different nature, in particular images, datasets, and software (overall almost 3%).

This is one of the reasons by which in the already mentioned LUMEN project GoTriple's content has been reorganised with the addition of dedicated indexes for media objects, datasets, and semantic artefacts. As the LUMEN project has made progress in this direction, we will consider this new organisation of GoTriple's data as the basis for the data model of the new KG.

3.2. The GoTriple KG Data Model

The kinds of data that the GoTriple KG will contain can be divided into three main categories, namely:

- Metadata related to SSH resources, as managed by the GoTriple discovery platform. They include, taking in consideration the ongoing evolutions of the LUMEN project, the following classes of elements:
 - metadata historically managed in GoTriple, including textual documents (articles, publications, books, book parts, ect), projects, and authors/researcher profiles
 - new classes of metadata related to datasets, semantic artefacts, and media objects;
- Metadata about datasets acquired through tools and instruments, as defined in the GRAPHIA WP3 workpackage (*Innovative Solutions and Instruments for the SSH KG*);
- entities extracted from the full text of documents by AI and NLP-powered services developed in GRAPHIA in the context of the WP4 workpackage (*Artificial Intelligence Solutions for the SSH KG*).

Finally, it must be possible to easily define correspondences between the newly created GoTriple KG and other scientific graphs, first and foremost those managed by GRAPHIA partners like OpenCitations, GESIS or ORKG. The latter point is the objective of the work conducted in T2.1 that aims to make these correspondences explicit through the GRAPHIA ontology, fully described in GRAPHIA deliverable D2.1. As such, we are not covering these aspects herein.

3.3. The TRIPLE Ontology as the basis for the GoTriple KG Data Model

GoTriple data model has been formally defined through the TRIPLE Ontology⁶ with the objective to provide a semantic web-compliant, machine understandable description of the main asset types of the platform. Developed in collaboration with domain experts, the ontology was crafted to achieve several key objectives: formalising the data model with semantic standards, defining controlled vocabularies, establishing connections with external entities, ensuring resource reusability, and maintaining detailed documentation for transparency and extensibility.

It is interesting to note that the definition of the ontology came later in the development of GoTriple. It has been in fact introduced to improve interoperability and encourage the reuse of GoTriple's content. Together with the ontology in fact, the platform's APIs have been expanded to also return RDF data formatted in JSON-LD according to the TRIPLE Ontology.

Its initial design was very simple, and almost completely used the Schema.org vocabulary. Later on, it has been expanded to provide a better formalisation by using other standard vocabularies including DC, FOAF, SIOC, and DataCite.

The ontology development followed a structured methodology, beginning with a preliminary analysis and employing the Simplified Agile Methodology for Ontology Development (SAMOD). This approach ensured a flexible, iterative development process with comprehensive testing and documentation, guaranteeing the ontology's accuracy and adaptability. Consequently, the ontology enhanced the semantic representation of research artefacts, promoted interoperability, and facilitated collaboration and knowledge reuse across the SSH domain.

Most of the recent work on the ontology has been done in the context of the ATRIUM project⁷, especially for what concerns the alignment with CIDOC-CRM, SSHOCro and SKG-IF. Its development is managed in the GitHub space of the ATRIUM project⁸ and it is openly accessible. The official URL of the ontology, accessible via content

⁶ <https://www.gotriple.eu/ontology/triple>

⁷ <https://atrium-research.eu/>

⁸ <https://github.com/atrium-research/triple-ontology>

negotiation both in RDF/XML and HTML formats is <https://gotriple.eu/ontology/triple>.

We provide below a description of each vocabulary that composes the TRIPLE ontology, dividing the presentation in two parts, one for the main classes and the other for the controlled vocabularies used to define the values of some of their properties.

3.3.1. Main classes

3.3.1.1. Document

The Document vocabulary models the core research artefact aggregated by GoTriple. A `triple:Document` is an academic resource as it appears on the discovery platform: mostly it consists of textual documents, like articles, text, thesis, book, book part, etc. Its definition has been aligned to standard ontologies to capture both bibliographic and web document aspects, while for specific properties (document type, conditions of access, and licenses) a stricter constraint has been defined with values defined in dedicated controlled vocabularies, still part of the TRIPLE ontology (see below).

As said, the design of the ontology followed the best practices of ontology modeling, including a wide reuse of standard vocabularies. In particular `triple:Document` is a subclass of both `schema:CreativeWork` and `foaf:Document`; it reuses and aligns to:

- FOAF (`foaf:Agent`, `foaf:Person`, `foaf:Organization`)
- DataCite identifier pattern (`datacite:Identifier`, `datacite:IdentifierScheme`, `datacite:hasIdentifier`, `datacite:usesIdentifierScheme`)
- Schema.org (e.g., `schema:author`, `schema:abstract`, `schema:Language`, `schema:Place`, `schema:DefinedTerm`, `schema:conditionsOfAccess`, etc.)
- SKOS (`skos:Concept`)
- SIOC (`sioc:topic`)
- FRAPO (`frapo:isOutputOf` to link the `triple:project` that produced this specific work)
- CIDOC-CRM (E31 Document)
- SSHOCro (SHE8 Publication)
- SKG-IF (`fabio:ScholarlyWork`).

A `triple:Cluster` is a special version of a `triple:Document`, as it regroups multiple duplicated documents into one. In GoTriple it appears as a “normal” document. Technically speaking a cluster is not a real document but a representation of the union of all the duplicate documents it represents. Its modeling reuses the `Collection` class of the Ontology Design Pattern⁹, reflecting the platform’s deduplication/versioning logic.

Documents carry identifiers via the DataCite pattern, with explicit `datacite:IdentifierScheme` individuals including `datacite:doi`, `datacite:handle`, `datacite:issn`, `datacite:isbn`, and `datacite:local-resource-identifier-scheme` for internal managed identifiers.

As said, document type, conditions of access, and license are limited to the imported SKOS schemes (`document_types`, `conditions_of_access`, `licenses`) of the TRIPLE Ontology (see below), enabling consistent curation and external mappings.

3.3.1.2. Project

The Project vocabulary models the research projects aggregated by GoTriple. A `triple:Project` represents the organizational and funding context in which scholarly artefacts are produced. For the moment it has been used to cover EU-funded projects from FP7, H2020 and Horizon EU Work-programmes but also citizen science initiatives managed in the VERA platform¹⁰, another OPERAS’ service.

A project in TRIPLE uses `schema:Project` as the core class, complemented with an explicit representation of grants, and temporal duration. Where appropriate, stricter constraints are applied (e.g., mandatory core literals and a required time interval), ensuring data quality and interoperability across heterogeneous sources.

The Project vocabulary reuses and aligns to:

- FOAF (`foaf:Agent`, `foaf:Person`, `foaf:Organization`);
- Schema.org (`schema:Grant`, plus literals such as `schema:description`, `schema:alternateName`);

⁹ <http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/cp/owl/collectionentity.owl>

¹⁰ <https://vera.operas-eu.org/>

- DataCite identifier pattern (datacite:Identifier, datacite:IdentifierScheme, datacite:hasIdentifier, datacite:usesIdentifierScheme) for grant identifiers;
- SIOC (sioc:topic) for topical tagging
- CIDOC-CRM (E7 Activity)
- SSHOCRo (SHE3 SSH Project)
- SKG-IF (Grant).

3.3.1.3. Profile

The Profile vocabulary models the person-centric entities aggregated by GoTriple. A profile represents the curated identity of a scholar or of an organization as it appears on the discovery platform and it is used to attach contribution roles (e.g. author, contributor) to documents, datasets, media objects, and semantic artefacts. It is also used to map registered users in the platform: it is important to note that the latter become visible in search results only if they are authors, that is, if they have successfully claimed the authorship of at least one publication found in GoTriple.

As the harvesting process might not distinguish when an author of a content type is an actual person or an organisation, in the TRIPLE ontology, the class `triple:Profile` has been defined as an extension of `foaf:Agent`, the superclass that extends both `foaf:Person` and `foaf:Organization`.

Other alignments with standard vocabularies defined in `triple:Profile` include:

- FOAF (`foaf:OnlineAccount`, `foaf:account`, `foaf:name`);
- DataCite identifier pattern (`datacite:Identifier`, `datacite:IdentifierScheme`, `datacite:hasIdentifier`, `datacite:usesIdentifierScheme`)—with dedicated schemes for agents and online accounts;
- SKG-IF (`Agent`).

3.3.1.4. Dataset

The Dataset class in TRIPLE is represented using `schema:Dataset` and `dc:Dataset`. It reuses and aligns to:

- Schema.org (schema:headline, schema:abstract, schema:Place, schema:publisher, schema:provider, schema:author, schema:contributor, schema:funding, schema:temporalCoverage, etc.)
- FOAF (foaf:Person, foaf:Organization as ranges for contributor/author/publisher/provider).
- DataCite identifier pattern (datacite:hasIdentifier, datacite:Identifier)
- FRAPO (frapo:isOutputOf to link the triple:project that produced this specific work)
- DDCMI Terms (dcterms:isReferencedBy to point to a triple:document that relates to this specific work)
- SIOC (sioc:topic)
- SSHOCro (SHEI Dataset)
- SKG-IF (fabio:Dataset).

It is important to also point out that WP3's data from tools and instruments will be aligned with triple:datasets. In GRAPHIA (both GoTriple and the KG) we are managing only metadata descriptions of these datasets: their actual data will be managed elsewhere and not inside the graph.

3.3.1.5. Media Object

The MediaObject vocabulary models multimedia items associated with GoTriple resources. A triple:MediaObject represents files such as images, audio, or video that accompany scholarly artefacts on the platform, carrying descriptive, technical, and provenance-related metadata consistent with the TRIPLE Ontology.

In particular triple:MediaObject is a subclass of schema:MediaObject and reuses and aligns to:

- FOAF (foaf:Person, foaf:Organization as ranges for schema:publisher, schema:provider, schema:producer, schema:author, schema:contributor).
- DataCite identifier pattern (datacite:Identifier, datacite:hasIdentifier).
- Schema.org (schema:headline, schema:abstract, schema:inLanguage, schema:spatialCoverage, schema:temporalCoverage, schema:encodingFormat, schema:fileFormat, schema:duration, schema:size, etc)

- FRAPO (frapo:isOutputOf to link the triple:project that produced this specific work)
- DCMI Terms (dcterms:isReferencedBy to point to a triple:document that relates to this specific work)
- CIDOC-CRM (E90 Symbolic Object)
- SKG-IF (fabio:Work).

MediaObjects expose rich descriptive elements (titles, abstracts, languages), production and provision roles, spatial/temporal coverage, and basic technical characteristics (format, duration, size) to support discovery and reuse.

3.3.1.6. Semantic Artefact

The SemanticArtefact vocabulary models ontologies, vocabularies, taxonomies, and concept schemes represented in GoTriple. A triple:SemanticArtefact carries descriptive, identification, provenance, and linkage metadata consistent with the TRIPLE Ontology and it is defined as a subclass of mod:SemanticArtefact and schema:CreativeWork. It reuses and aligns to:

- Schema.org (schema:headline, schema:abstract, schema:author, schema:contributor, schema:publisher, schema:provider, schema:producer, schema:fileFormat, schema:encodingFormat, schema:version, schema:dateCreated, schema:datePublished, etc.).
- DataCite identifier pattern – datacite:hasIdentifier (→ datacite:Identifier).
- FOAF (foaf:Person and foaf:Organization as the ranges for contributor/author/publisher and related roles)
- FRAPO (frapo:isOutputOf to link the triple:project that produced this specific work)
- DCMI Terms (dcterms:isReferencedBy to point to a triple:document that relates to this specific work)
- CIDOC-CRM (E90 Symbolic Object)
- SKG-IF (fabio:Work).

3.3.2. Support vocabularies

The TRIPLE ontology provides specific authority files to assign controlled values to some of its main entities properties. In particular there are four specific vocabularies, “Discipline”, “License”, “Condition of Access”, and “Content type”, which are all formalised by using the SKOS ontology.

The “Disciplines” controlled vocabulary is a linked data resource that uses the SKOS ontology to provide a formalization of the SSH domain in 27 fields of study. This formalization is one of the outcomes of the TRIPLE project and exploits the vision of a former EU Funded research project (MORESS¹¹). In this vocabulary each discipline is linked to one or more corresponding concepts of other widely known classification systems, including the Library of Congress Subject Headings, Wikidata and the Dewey Decimal Classification. This vocabulary is also multilingual, with concepts available in English, Italian, French, and German.

“Content type” provides a linked data description of the admitted types by linking them to the corresponding resource types of the COAR Controlled Vocabularies for Repositories¹².

Finally, licences and conditions of access were created by analysing the most common metadata retrieved in GoTriple data after an initial harvesting of data. The purpose was therefore to standardise and normalise the metadata received as input from the various sources.

A description of the ontological aspects of these authority files follow.

Even if not strictly related to the TRIPLE Ontology it is worth mentioning a crucial taxonomy for GoTriple data, the TRIPLE Vocabulary¹³. It is another significant outcome of the TRIPLE project and it consists of a rich controlled vocabulary of 3,375 linked data SSH-related concepts. It has been formalized in SKOS and provides translations in 11 languages. This vocabulary is not part of the TRIPLE Ontology as it is used only as a linked data resource: therefore it will not be described in this deliverable.

¹¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/HPSE-CT-2002-60060>

¹² <https://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org>

¹³ <https://www.semantics.gr/authorities/vocabularies/SSH-LCSH/vocabulary-entries?language=en>

3.3.2.1. Discipline

The Disciplines authority file (prefix `tdisc`) formalises top-level SSH subject areas. It is published as a SKOS concept scheme so that disciplines can be used consistently for classification, faceted search, analytics, and cross-platform interoperability. Concepts (e.g., Archaeology and Prehistory, Communication Sciences, Environmental Studies, History, Linguistics, Sociology) are provided with multilingual preferred labels (EN/FR/DE/IT) and are explicitly aligned to external authorities to support high-quality interoperability and recommendations.

As with the rest of TRIPLE, the design follows reuse-first practices and aligns to:

- SKOS (`skos:Concept`, `skos:ConceptScheme`, `skos:inScheme`, `skos:hasTopConcept`, `skos:closeMatch`, `skos:exactMatch`) for the core concept model and mappings.
- DataCite Identifiers (`datacite:Identifier`, `datacite:IdentifierScheme`, `datacite:hasIdentifier`, `datacite:usesIdentifierScheme`).
- Dublin Core / VANN / schema.org for ontology metadata (`dct:title`, `dct:abstract`, `vann:preferredNamespacePrefix`, `schema:creativeWorkStatus`).

Each discipline is an individual `skos:Concept` in the single scheme `tdisc:disciplines`. Every concept is linked to one local code identifier via `datacite:hasIdentifier`, and that identifier names its scheme with `datacite:usesIdentifierScheme`. Crosswalks use `skos:exactMatch` and `skos:closeMatch` to connect concepts to multiple external authorities, including:

- LCSH and SSH-LCSH subjects (e.g., Art, Demography, Law, Psychology);
- DDC entries exposed as SKOS concepts inside the file (e.g., 34 Law, 90–99 History, 384 Telecommunications);
- CESSDA Topic Classification (e.g., Education, Politics, Media, Natural Environment);
- Wikidata concepts (e.g., Q309 History, Q8162 Linguistics, Q36442 Political science)
- TRIPLE Vocabulary entities (e.g. `sh2003003668` Literatures, `sh2005003729` Arts and history).

3.3.2.2. Content Type

The Content Type authority file (prefix tdoc) formalises the set of research output categories used across GoTriple. It is published as a SKOS concept scheme so that types can be applied consistently for classification, faceted search, analytics, and cross-platform interoperability.

Concepts (e.g., Article, Book, Conference, Dataset, Periodical, Preprint, Report, Review, Software, Text, Thesis, Bibliography, Blog post, Image, Video, Sound, Learning object, Manuscript, Map) are provided with English preferred labels and are explicitly aligned to external authorities to support high-quality interoperability and recommendations.

This is the list of the reused ontologies:

- SKOS (skos:Concept, skos:ConceptScheme, skos:inScheme, skos:hasTopConcept, skos:closeMatch, skos:exactMatch) for the core concept model and mappings.
- DataCite Identifiers (datacite:Identifier, datacite:IdentifierScheme, datacite:hasIdentifier, datacite:usesIdentifierScheme).
- Dublin Core / VANN / schema.org for ontology metadata (dct:title, dct:creator, dct:contributor, vann:preferredNamespacePrefix, schema:creativeWorkStatus).

Each document type is an individual skos:Concept in the single scheme tdoc:documentType. Every concept is linked to one local code identifier via datacite:hasIdentifier, and that identifier declares its scheme with datacite:usesIdentifierScheme. Crosswalks use skos:exactMatch to the COAR Resource Types vocabulary¹⁴ so records can be exchanged and reasoned over reliably.

Two catch-all values preserve source information without loss:

- tdoc:other: the source states a type that is out of scope of the controlled list.
- tdoc:undefined: the source provides no type at all.

¹⁴ https://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/resource_types/

3.3.2.3. License

The License authority file (prefix `tlic`) formalises a controlled set of licensing families used across GoTriple. It is published as a SKOS concept scheme so that licence information can be captured consistently for classification, faceted filtering, analytics, and cross-platform interoperability.

Concepts (e.g., Creative Commons, Open Data, Open source, CLARIN-ACA, CLARIN-RES, Clarin Pub, ELRA licences, Meta-Share, Microsoft Public Licence, Microsoft Reciprocal Licence) are provided with English preferred labels and give a lightweight normalisation of licence statements supplied by data sources.

As with the rest of TRIPLE, the design follows reuse-first practices and aligns to:

- SKOS (`skos:Concept`, `skos:ConceptScheme`, `skos:inScheme`, `skos:hasTopConcept`, `skos:closeMatch`, `skos:exactMatch`) for the core concept model and mappings.
- DataCite Identifiers (`datacite:Identifier`, `datacite:IdentifierScheme`, `datacite:hasIdentifier`, `datacite:usesIdentifierScheme`).
- Dublin Core / VANN / schema.org for ontology metadata (`dct:title`, `dct:creator`, `dct:contributor`, `vann:preferredNamespacePrefix`, `schema:creativeWorkStatus`).

Each licence family is an individual `skos:Concept` in the single scheme `tlic:licenses`. Every concept is linked to one local code identifier via `datacite:hasIdentifier`, and that identifier declares its scheme with `datacite:usesIdentifierScheme`. The scheme is intentionally coarse-grained: it captures widely used licence families and provider frameworks (e.g., Creative Commons, CLARIN, ELRA, META-SHARE, OSI/“open source”, Microsoft licences) rather than enumerating every specific licence text or version.

Two catch-all values preserve source information without loss:

- `tlic:other`: the source states a licence outside the controlled list.
- `tlic:undefined`: the source provides no licence.

3.3.2.4. Condition of Access

The Condition of Access authority file (prefix `tcoa`) formalises top-level access modalities for resources aggregated in GoTriple. It is published as a SKOS concept scheme so that access status can be captured consistently for discovery, faceted filtering, analytics, and cross-platform interoperability. Concepts include Open Access, Free Access, Closed Access, Public Domain, Restricted access or use, All Rights Reserved, plus the catch-alls Other and Undefined.

As with the rest of TRIPLE, the design follows reuse-first practices and aligns to:

- SKOS (`skos:Concept`, `skos:ConceptScheme`, `skos:inScheme`, `skos:hasTopConcept`, `skos:closeMatch`, `skos:exactMatch`) for the core concept model and mappings.
- DataCite Identifiers (`datacite:Identifier`, `datacite:IdentifierScheme`, `datacite:hasIdentifier`, `datacite:usesIdentifierScheme`).
- Dublin Core / VANN / schema.org for ontology metadata (`dct:title`, `dct:creator`, `dct:contributor`, `vann:preferredNamespacePrefix`, `schema:creativeWorkStatus`).

Each access condition is an individual `skos:Concept` in the single scheme `tcoa:conditionsOfAccess`. Every concept is linked to exactly one local code identifier via `datacite:hasIdentifier`, and that identifier declares its governing scheme with `datacite:usesIdentifierScheme`.

3.4. Extension of the TRIPLE Ontology for the management of entities extracted from text

The TRIPLE ontology has been also extended to take into account:

- the entities extracted from the full-text of documents via the WP4 services
- their relationship with the original document
- and the possible relationships amongst themselves.

We present here a first proposal that includes the first two points mentioned above, while for describing the actual relationships amongst entities the use of standard ontologies, yet to be identified, will be the suggested option. It is too early on the other hand to analyse this topic in detail, as the actual results will be strictly

dependent from the capabilities of WP4 services, whose development hasn't started yet at this stage of the project.

Regarding the need to model the relationship of entities extracted from documents, we need a predicate that can express in a clear way the origin of this information. Among the options considered, a first one was the PROV-O¹⁵ Ontology, which has been designed to represent provenance information generated in different systems and under different contexts. "PROV defines a core data model for provenance for building representations of the entities, people and processes involved in producing a piece of data or thing in the world"¹⁶.

In particular, we considered *prov:wasDerivedFrom*, which asserts a derivation between two *prov:Entity* individuals (its domain and range). Classifying triple:Document as a *prov:Entity* is not a problem, as anything can be a PROV entity. The issue is semantic: using *prov:wasDerivedFrom* between a real-world entity (e.g., a person) and a document would incorrectly imply the person is derived from the document.

Another option that we considered was using the *schema:mentions* of *schema:org*: this option is coherent with the data model in which all classes are aligned with *schema:CreativeWork* and its subclasses, while the extracted entity can be any instance of *schema:Thing*, which is "the most generic type of item"¹⁷.

While this solves the problem of linking the document to its extracted entities, it loses the information about how this extraction process took place. For this purpose, an annotation can be created to provide this level of details: the annotation will be using the W3C Web Annotation Data Model¹⁸ (oa) and have the document as target and the extracted entities as bodies. Moreover the annotation can also include metadata about the extraction process, again specified in oa properties, including the service responsible for the entity extraction (oa:creator) and the timestamp of the extraction action (oa:created).

An example of how to represent all this follows:

```
:d a triple:Document ;  
  schema:mentions :AdaLovelace, :Paris .
```

¹⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

¹⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/NOTE-prov-primer-20130430/>

¹⁷ <https://schema.org/Thing>

¹⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-model>


```
:AdaLovelace a schema:Person ;
    skos:exactMatch <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q7259> .

:Paris a schema:Place ;
    skos:exactMatch <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q90> .

:annotation a oa:Annotation ;
    oa:hasTarget :d ;
    oa:hasBody :AdaLovelace, :Paris ;
    oa:creator "wp4_service" ;
    oa:created "2025-11-17T12:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTime .
```

In WP4 there has been a first analysis of the possible type of entities to extract from textual documents. This list is presented in the first column of the table 3.1 below: for each type of entity we also propose possible corresponding classes of standard ontologies widely used in the SSH domain, including schema.org, FOAF¹⁹ or CIDOC-CRM²⁰, together with the classes of the TRIPLE Ontology described before.

When in some situations the classes of different ontologies were proposed, we cited their name.

<i>Type of entity</i>	<i>Corresponding classes</i>
Person	schema:Person, foaf:Person, cidoc:E21_Person
Organization	schema:Organization, foaf:Organization, org:Organization (W3C org) ²¹
Event	schema:Event, cidoc:E5_Event
Place	schema:Place, dcterms:Location, cidoc:E53_Place
Point of Interest	schema:Place, gn:Feature (Geonames) ²² , cidoc:E27_Site
Time Period	dcterms:PeriodOfTime, cidoc:E52_Time-Span, time:ProperInterval (Time Ontology) ²³

¹⁹ <http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec/>

²⁰ <https://cidoc-crm.org/>

²¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-org/>

²² <https://www.geonames.org/ontology/documentation.html>

²³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/owl-time/>

Cultural Object	schema:CreativeWork, cidoc:E22_Man-Made_Object
Archival Metadata	dcterms:BibliographicResource, rico:Record or rico:RecordSet (RiC-O) ²⁴
Citation	cito:Citation (CiTO) ²⁵
Publication	triple:Document, foaf:Document, fabio:ScholarlyWork (SKG-O) ²⁶
Project	triple:Project, schema:ResearchProject, foaf:Project
Dataset	triple:Dataset, schema:Dataset, fabio:Dataset (SKG-O)
Semantic Artefact	triple:SemanticArtefact, mod:SemanticArtefact (MOD) ²⁷
Software	schema:SoftwareApplication, fabio:Software (SKG-O)

Table 3.1 – Possible classes of entities extracted from text

3.5. Using RDF Named Graphs

To ease the management of the information in the graph, we propose the use of Named Graphs²⁸ or “quads” to group all RDF triples associated with a single instance of the TRIPLE Ontology created by the Data Acquisition Platform.

This way, each document, profile, project, dataset and semantic artefact will correspond to a named graph. For documents, the named graph will also include all the entities extracted from its text via WP4 services as described in the previous section.

All the information related to an instance will be contained within specific boundaries, easing all the updates, replacements, and removal operations.

²⁴ <https://www.ica.org/resource/records-in-contexts-ontology/>

²⁵ <https://sparontologies.github.io/cito/current/cito.html>

²⁶ <https://w3id.org/skg-if/ontology/>

²⁷ <https://fair-impact.github.io/MOD/index-en.html>

²⁸ See <https://www.w3.org/TR/n-quads/>

Moreover, it will also be possible to include provenance metadata that describes the generation process of the data contained in the named graph or to manage data versioning, by keeping different versions of the data in different quads.

Named graphs are supported by Virtuoso and should soon be supported by Qlever as well²⁹. This will allow this strategy to be applied in GRAPHIA independently of the final technology used for the implementation of the GoTriple KG (see on that chapter 5).

²⁹ See Qlever issue about this feature <https://github.com/ad-freiburg/qlever/pull/1337>

4. Data Acquisition Platform

The main purpose of the Data Acquisition Platform (DAP) is feeding the GoTriple KG with data acquired from sources, curated, enriched and extracted by a set of processing services. The GoTriple KG will complement GoTriple by:

- proposing a graph vision of all metadata contained in its indexes;
- providing access to a significant amount of newly generated data, extracted from GoTriple's documents' text via advanced NLP and AI-based services, developed in the context of the WP4 workpackage.

While inevitably at the beginning GoTriple will be a source of data to populate the GoTriple KG, when fully operational the DAP can also update GoTriple's indexes. In fact data sources will be the same for both services, as it is the same the curation logic of content's metadata: only the finalisation differs, with an RDF output for the GoTriple KG and a JSON format for the Elasticsearch-based GoTriple's indexes.

Moreover, as explained below, the DAP aims at being a scalable and performant architecture that can improve on the performance of the present GoTriple processing pipeline SCORE. It makes sense therefore to imagine as the final evolution to have with the DAP a common processing service for the GoTriple KG and GoTriple.

In this chapter an initial design of the platform is presented: while the main technological decisions have been taken, some open points remain, in particular concerning the selection of the most suitable technologies to use for its implementation.

4.1. Requirements of the platform

Below are presented the main requirements that guided the architectural design of the DAP.

One processing platform only

The DAP must feed both the GoTriple KG and GoTriple. In an initial phase, while the DAP is still under development, the existing GoTriple indexes will act as a data source for the GoTriple KG, with their content converted into RDF format to populate the graph. Once the DAP is fully implemented, it will replace the current pipeline used to

feed GoTriple and become the single, unified platform responsible for ingesting, processing, and updating data for both GoTriple and the GoTriple KG.

Speed and Scalability

The DAP must be fast and scalable, being able to recreate and update the indexes and the graph "relatively" quickly. It must be capable of processing and rebuilding GoTriple's indexes and the graph in a matter of hours or within a few days at a maximum.

Scalability will allow the processing services to improve their capacity by increasing the number of resources on which they run. Specific technologies (in particular OKD/Kubernetes which is used at PCSS) must be taken into account for this purpose.

Big Data in Volume

The DAP must process and manage a large amount of data (Volume), even if not necessarily generated at extremely fast pace (no Velocity) or so diversified in nature and structure (no Variety), as it will always ingest textual metadata descriptions.

Processing steps based on the microservice design pattern

Each processing step will be implemented by microservices, each with minimal mutual dependencies. This allows individual services to be developed using the most appropriate technologies and programming languages, and to be evolved or replaced independently as requirements change.

Compared to a monolithic architecture, this approach introduces additional operational complexity (e.g. service orchestration and asynchronous communication), but it significantly improves modularity, extensibility, and maintainability. In particular, the microservice-based design supports incremental integration of new data sources and processing steps, as well as the evolution of existing components, while limiting the impact of these changes to the DAP as a whole.

Support of both incremental and batch updates

When operational, the DAP will apply incremental updates. At the same time it must support batch updates, that is updates of a significant mass of data not recently harvested.

Batch updates can be full (rebuilding the whole GoTriple KG and GoTriple's indexes) or partial, the latter based on time (e.g. only data changed in the last two months) or associated to the result of a specific microservice (e.g. all DOIs recognised by the Data Normalisation microservice).

This allows to relaunch full or partial reindex operations to add newly generated data (e.g. a new processing microservice added in the architecture) or to correct processing bugs.

No sequential processing and no blocking points

We want to remove dependencies from single services that can become bottlenecks (e.g. the translation service, AI-based services, or other processing operations in GoTriple that are inherently slow).

Eventual consistency

This is a consequence of the previous points: data in both the GoTriple KG and GoTriple will be gradually enriched and completed as soon as the various microservices produce the results of their processing.

In this context, eventual consistency describes the relationship between data imported from multiple external sources and their representation in GoTriple and in the GoTriple KG. Updates propagated from the original sources are not required to be completely synchronized at once, but are instead progressively aligned over time.

Respecting this requirement will also improve the overall robustness of the architecture.

4.2. Description of the architecture

For designing the DAP the requirements were taken into account together with the experience of project partners in the development of similar platforms. PCSS in fact has implemented DACE (Data Aggregation and proCessing Engine)³⁰, a multi-module, large scale processing system designed for container platforms for the harvesting and processing of cultural content. Foxcub has developed the content

³⁰ <https://gitlab.pcss.pl/dl-team/aggregation/dace>

acquisition platform that feeds Matilda³¹, a bibliographic platform for open science that at present indexes over 155 million publications. Finally, Net7 has developed SCRE (Semantic Content Retrieval Engine)³² which is the content acquisition and processing pipeline of GoTriple.

The architecture has been structured in three main components:

- *Services*, which directly manage data, from content retrieval, metadata processing and enrichment to the publishing on the front-end systems, that is the GoTriple KG and GoTriple
- *Data Layer*, that stores the data processed by the single services. The output of a service may be the input for one or more other services.
- *Event bus*, which orchestrates the processing amongst the various services.

As indicated in the requirements of the previous section (4.1), each **service** will be implemented as an autonomous microservice, deployed within a scalable processing environment that supports orchestration, execution, and monitoring. Two services have a particular importance, that is, the *Harvester*, that will import content from multiple sources, and the *Publisher*, that will update the GoTriple KG and GoTriple's indexes.

The Harvester's behaviour must be configurable: through a web interface it must be possible to add a new source by specifying the data-retrieval parameters, including the harvesting protocol or access mechanism (e.g. OAI-PMH, REST APIs, or downloadable file dumps), together with the relevant endpoints and query parameters needed to fetch the content.

The **Data layer** will be based on the "Polyglot Persistence" paradigm, that is the principle of using multiple data storage technologies, choosing the best repository for each specific need. In particular all data that must be quickly retrieved by the services for their processing will reside on a scalable Data Store, designed to support increasing data volumes and query throughput by adding resources incrementally, without requiring disruptive architectural changes. "Cold data", that is information that doesn't necessitate to be promptly retrieved and that might unnecessarily bloat data store's indexes (in particular if their overall dimension is remarkable), can be stored in an Object Storage.

³¹ <https://matilda.science/>

³² <https://zenodo.org/records/7708784>

Finally, the **Event Bus** is the orchestrator of the events that activate the services. It will consist of a massively scalable Message Oriented Middleware in which multiple queues will be configured, to drive the processing of interdependent services.

The proposed architecture of the DAP is shown in the diagram below (figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1 – High level architecture of the Data Acquisition Platform

The communication between services will be based on specific queues implemented into the Event Bus. Every service therefore, as indicated in the architecture:

- reads and writes on the Data Layer
- is triggered by receiving a message from the Event Bus and posts a message when its processing is over, to activate the next service(s).

An example of these chain of events is represented in the diagram below. Here we have decomposed the complete expected processing of content by the DAP in steps, each one implemented by a single service. The detailed description of these services is presented in section 4.4 but we anticipate them here to better present the logic flow of information performed by the DAP.

Figure 4.2 – Processing flow of the Data Acquisition Platform

We want to put in place an Eventual Consistency model, in which a single piece of content is gradually updated in the front-end systems, as long as each service of the DAP has completed the processing of its data. To manage the processing, “messages” in the Event Bus will be exchanged amongst all services.

The arrows in the diagram show the flow of data, starting from the *Harvester* that, as indicated, will acquire content from multiple sources. Every piece of data retrieved by the Harvester (a document, a project, a semantic artefact, a media object item, or a dataset) will be normally processed on a one-by-one basis, unless, for performance reasons, it is preferable to batch-process them (as it is the case, for example, for the Publisher).

After normalisation several services are triggered in parallel: the output of some of them might be already used by the Publisher service to update the GoTriple KG and GoTriple. This is the case for the Keywords Extraction and Classification services.

Other services will be dependent on the output of others, like Automatic Translation that needs the output of Language Recognition, of the Annotator, dependent on the Classification service, or of the Entity and Relation Extraction services, those based on NLP and AI that will be implemented in the context of WP4. The latter services might also need extracted and normalised keywords produced by the Keyword Extraction service.

4.3. Technological stack

The technological stack that composes the DAP, as any other development done in GRAPHIA, will be based on open source software. All the implementations will be hosted at PCSS. We present in this section an overview of the proposed software to use for implementing the various components of the DAP: finalising the technological stack to use for the development of this platform is the next important step to be taken in the context of the T2.3 task.

4.3.1. Communication and event streaming in the Event Bus

As said, DAP will be implemented as a set of microservices. Internal communication between microservices will be handled by the open source Apache Kafka³³ platform. Kafka is a flexible and easily scalable software that allows messages to be exchanged between different microservices through different channels. In addition, Kafka provides mechanisms to track message consumption and processing status, allowing services to determine whether an incoming message has been successfully processed and, if necessary, to reprocess it. As a result, the system is robust to temporary failures, as unprocessed messages remain available and can be consumed again once the relevant services resume operation.

4.3.2. Data Store

As presented above, this is one of the two components of the Data Layer. DAP microservices need to permanently store their data, not only to support the normal operation of the platform but also to enable reindexing, full or partial, if need arises.

Coherent with the microservice design pattern, every service can choose the best data storage option that satisfies its needs. However, to simplify operation activities, it is advisable to limit the number of software systems that compose the DAP.

At the current stage of analysis, two types of open source storage software have been identified:

³³ <https://kafka.apache.org/>

- RDBMS, like PostgreSQL³⁴ in High Availability (HA) configuration
- Search engines, in particular Elasticsearch³⁵.

PostgreSQL HA provides a classic, traditional SQL approach but with increased availability. When microservices need fast searching capabilities (e.g. for author disambiguation), a search engine can be a better solution. Elasticsearch is an open source, distributed, scalable, search engine, which is already used by previous developments of GoTriple.

The implementation of the data store will be limited to one of these two systems or at most both of them, in case there is an explicit value to manage data in two storage applications. One of the possible reasons for this is due to the potential reuse of existing code for the development of the DAP components from the existing platforms (DACE, SCRE, and Matilda).

4.3.4. Object Storage

The object storage is the other component of the Data Layer: it will be based on an S3-compatible object storage service, hosted within the PCSS infrastructure. PCSS has long-standing experience in operating S3-compatible storage services and currently supports several large-scale European research infrastructures, including the Europeana eCloud project. The PCSS storage solution fully implements the S3 protocol, allowing GRAPHIA to benefit from the broad ecosystem of existing tools, libraries, and software components developed for S3-based environments, while remaining independent from vendor-specific cloud services.

The object storage will host derived and auxiliary resources produced by the DAP, including translated metadata and entities extracted from full-text documents. These resources are not intended for direct search and therefore are not stored in the data store, but they are required for subsequent processing steps.

³⁴ <https://www.postgresql.org/>

³⁵ <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch>

4.3.5. Microservices

The microservices themselves can be implemented in any programming language that allows communication with the event bus, the data store and the S3 storage and that can implement the REST interface, however we plan to use mainly Java and Python. For the development of some of the microservices mentioned here, it will be also possible to reuse the current implementations done for the SCRE, DACE, and Matilda.

4.4. Service components

We present here a first list of possible DAP microservices, based on the expected processing needs of the platform and on the previous experience of GRAPHIA partners in similar projects. For implementing these services the corresponding components of SCRE, DACE and Matilda will be analysed to evaluate their potential reuse or refactoring in the context of GRAPHIA.

All services will be deployed as containerised components, managed through Kubernetes-compatible pods. This approach simplifies development and especially the deployment of the DAP in production in an OKD based infrastructure at PCSS. Each service can be deployed independently, with its assigned resources tailored to its actual processing needs and dynamically adjusted according to the current workload of the platform.

4.4.1. Harvester

It must allow to continuously import and process metadata from multiple and diverse sources, including large publications aggregators (BASE, DOAJ, OpenAire, Isidore), national repositories alike (Hrčak, Biblioteka Nauki, ZRC Sazu, EKT, Recyt or Pombaline) but also dedicated platforms that manage datasets (e.g. CKAN, Geonetwork), projects (CORDIS), or semantic artefacts (OntoPortal).

Its logic must be completely configurable, so that it is possible to add another data source through a web-based control dashboard. It must include multiple connectors to interoperate with a large set of data sources: the protocols and standards that must support include OAI-PMH with multiple data models (DC, EDM, XOAI, MARC21,

ISO 19115, EAD), together with ad-hoc connectors implemented to interact with specific platforms (e.g. OpenAIRE graph or Mod-API for OntoPortal).

The harvester builds upon the corresponding component of the SCRE pipeline, which provides an easy to use, configurable web interface for controlling the import flow of new content sources, as shown in the picture below.

Create a new source

Please insert your details and data to create a new source.

Name
New data source

Typology
OAI PMH

URL address
https://domain.edu/oai-pmh

Metadata prefix
- None -
- None -
base_dc
xocai
edm
oai_dc

Figure 4.3 – The configurable harvester web interface of the SCRE pipeline

4.4.2. Data Normalisation

Harvesting data from different sources poses a challenge in terms of both quality and diversity of the retrieved metadata. The Data Normalisation service aims at producing a consistent, and possibly improved, output by processing the original metadata acquired by the connectors of the Harvester. As the data models of each source varies, it is essential to normalise the information received to the internal standard designed for the DAP, which essentially reflects the formalisation of the TRIPLE Ontology described in chapter 3. We call it the “Internal Message Format” (IMF).

The first thing that this service must perform is the discrimination of the data type among those managed by the platform (Documents, Projects, Datasets, Semantic Artefacts, and Media Object items). The mapping rules of each source and connector of the Harvesting component vary according to the nature of the metadata schema of the data source.

It is practically impossible to have a full alignment of the acquired metadata with the TRIPLE ontology and this is particularly true with less expressive descriptive formats such as OAI-PMH Dublin Core (DC). For example, to identify a single attribute, several elements in the original metadata must be analysed and searched for. This is due to the fact that very often data providers don't fully follow the standards either due to limitations in their expressivity or for different interpretations of them. This forces the Data Normalisation service to apply several strategies to recognise the metadata element to map in the corresponding field of the IMF.

For example, for OAI-PMH DC normally publishers use the same element, `dc:rights`, to indicate both the access rights (`conditionOfAccess`) and the licence of the document. It is therefore the Data Normalisation service that takes care of distinguishing between these two cases.

Moreover the Data Normalisation service must also try and correct possible errors in the original metadata through heuristics like those indicated below:

- impossible dates of publication, e.g. “0” or “512”;
- missing or wrong association with languages in the textual elements “title” and “abstract”;
- inconsistent use of labels and codes to indicate the language (e.g. “en”, “en_US”, “eng” always for the English language);
- use of free textual descriptions to specify the type of the publication and, especially, the licence and access rights.

These are just examples of the typical “bad data” received from data sources given the extensive experience done by GRAPHIA partners in harvesting data for GoTriple, Matilda and via the DACE platform.

What follows is a first proposal of metadata curation that the Data Normalisation service must perform:

- removing metadata duplicates when they appear;

- cleaning textual strings, by trimming leading and trailing spaces and punctuation elements, plus removing any markup such as HTML tags;
- associating values from controlled vocabularies for some normalised elements.

It is important to point out that original “dirty” metadata must be maintained in dedicated elements of the IMF. This guarantees the possibility to access the original metadata, while the normalised elements allow for a better presentation and more effective filtering of search results in the front-end systems.

4.4.3. Language recognition and automatic translation

The purpose of this service is to associate the correct language description to the retrieved textual metadata (mainly title and abstracts). This is necessary because often language metadata is missing or wrong. Also, language elements are very often expressed without using any standard, e.g. with string in local languages (e.g. “inglese”, “italiano”, “français”) or abbreviations (“en”, “eng”,...). They must therefore be identified through a series of pattern matching rules and normalised to a subset of ISO standards (e.g. ISO-639-1) codes. When the language specified in the metadata element is not identifiable, the result is set to “other”, while when the language is missing from the element it is considered “undefined”.

Understanding the exact language provided for these textual descriptions is also fundamental to decide if an automatic translation must be applied or not.

In fact for GoTriple, in order to guarantee the widest fruition of its content, an English translation for titles and abstracts is always provided if it is missing from the original metadata. For this purpose the eTranslation³⁶ service is used. It is operated by CEF-Digital, a public European infrastructure which provides free tools, support and funding for building digital services. It provides good quality machine translation for all the official languages of the EU as well as Ukrainian, Chinese, Russian and Turkish.

³⁶ https://translation.ec.europa.eu/tools-and-resources/ai-translation-and-language-tools_en

4.4.4. Keywords Extraction

This service must normalise the textual keywords associated with the content retrieved from original sources. Given the previous experience in the aforementioned projects, it has been decided to limit curation to a minimum set of actions, including removing duplicates or trimming the blank spaces before and after every string or normalising the language attribute associated with them if present by using a controlled vocabulary.

4.4.5. Entity and relation extraction

This component will interact with the services implemented in the context of WP4 for extracting entities and additional metadata from textual documents, by reusing both their textual descriptions (title, abstract, keywords) and, when available, the full text of the publication.

The final list of WP4 services hasn't been finalised yet, but amongst them the following have been already approved:

- entity extraction, that is, the possibility to obtain the entities described in section 3.4, that will be linked to instances of triple:document. Possibly together with these entities it will be also possible to store in the graph relationships amongst them.
- citations extractions
- automatic classification (see next point).

Other possible data curation and enrichment functionalities that are currently in discussion include:

- authors and affiliations extraction from PDF articles. This might help to improve the metadata quality especially for sources harvested via OAI-PMH DC, whose data model is quite limited. We expect from this service to obtain a clear distinction between the authors' name and their affiliation, together with their ORCID IDs if present
- language identification: AI based services might be more efficient than the NLP based libraries used at present in GoTriple in those cases in which the text presents sentences in multiple languages (e.g. titles that contain in the same string a version in the original language together with the English translation).

4.4.6. Classification

The Classification service developed for GoTriple automatically assigns SSH disciplinary categories to documents using the MORESS taxonomy (27 categories), relying on a multilingual neural-network model trained on nearly one million manually categorised records. Titles, abstracts and keywords are preprocessed (cleaning, lemmatisation, n-grams) before being vectorised and fed to a sigmoid-based multi-label classifier, producing a relevance score for each discipline. Integrated as an autonomous microservice in the DAP, it exposes a REST API that processes documents in near real-time; only categories above a quality threshold and up to a maximum of two are retained, ensuring precision and user trust.

The service is continuously evaluated through Quality Control workshops using rank plots, F1-scores, category distribution analyses and confusion matrices, allowing iterative refinement of models and thresholds. Built on an open-source stack (Python, TensorFlow/Keras, SpaCy, Flask/Gunicorn, Docker, Prometheus/Grafana), it provides a robust, standardised and reusable component for enriching the GoTriple KG and the GoTriple indexes with high-quality disciplinary metadata.

In parallel, GRAPHIA is developing a new AI-based classifier, leveraging few-shot learning and semantic alignment, which aims to automatically categorise content based on predefined vocabularies and may progressively replace the current model as part of future KG enrichment workflows.

4.4.7. Annotation

The Annotation service used for GoTriple enriches textual metadata by detecting fine-grained SSH concepts from the TRIPLE Vocabulary through a deterministic NLP approach that complements statistical discipline classification. It relies on a multilingual SKOS subset of LCSH and performs semantic matching via extensive text normalisation (case, accents, inflections, stop-words) to identify precise vocabulary labels in titles, abstracts and keywords. After building an optimised multilingual index, the service processes documents in near real-time through a REST API and applies a two-step filtering strategy, blacklist removal of generic or noisy terms, and structural filtering based on shared SKOS parent concept, to retain only the most relevant tags. Built on Python, SpaCy, Flask/Gunicorn and Docker, and monitored through

Prometheus and Grafana, the service has shown strong performance, with blacklist optimisation reducing noise by more than 30% and structural grouping improving contextual coherence. Ongoing refactoring focuses on generalising vocabulary ingestion, making structural filtering optional, improving configuration flexibility, and maintaining efficient annotation across heterogeneous SKOS vocabularies.

4.4.8. Deduplication

Identifying duplicates is not an easy task because of the differences normally found in metadata describing the same object (e.g. a publication). For example, for a single document we could have different identifiers, in particular DOIs written in different and non standard ways, titles with extra parts or with additional punctuation elements, and authors written in alternative ways (e.g. “Francesca Di Donato”, “Di Donato, F.”, “Donato, Francesca Di”, ...).

This service should try to identify duplicates by confronting:

- standard Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) if present (e.g. DOI, or handle.net)
- the title. It is important to try and normalise it first by applying punctuation removal, transformation from Unicode to ASCII (e.g. for content in Greek or Cyrillic), putting all letters in lowercase, and trimming blank characters at the beginning and at the end
- the year of publication
- the authors, in number but possibly also with their names.

4.4.9. Author attribution

The goal of this microservice is to recognise when a new content ingested in the DAP can be associated with an already processed author. This task, which seems quite simple and straight-forward, poses in reality a lot of problems, including:

- it is not easy to recognise “real persons”: sometimes in fact we have as authors things like “Department of Computer Science” or “ACM Conference 2021”;
- a single person might be spelled in a different way, e.g. “Suzanne Dumouchel”, “Dumouchel, Suzanne”, “Dumouchel, S.”;
- there might be homonyms among authors.

The authors attribution service should try to solve this problem by using rules based on:

- a normalisation of the author's name, by including all possible variants (e.g. "Dumouchel, Suzanne" -> "Suzanne Dumouchel", "Dumouchel, S.")
- the year of the publication
- the publisher, which often represents the Research Centre the author is associated with
- the keywords of the publication.

By comparing all these elements, the service tries to determine whether a given author entry is a duplicate of an existing one. For example, two homonyms who publish in different time periods and on unrelated topics are recognised as different individuals. Conversely, variations of the same name (e.g., "Dumouchel, Suzanne" and "Dumouchel, S.") may refer to the same author if the other criteria align, for instance, if the publications fall within the same temporal range and several keywords match.

4.4.10. Publisher

This microservice will be responsible for the update of the front-end systems using the "eventual consistency" approach described above. It will also coalesce multiple data sources of the same provider into a single flow of publication: this is needed as very often content providers publish their data via multiple endpoints, OAI-PMH sets or file dumps. The service will take care of updating both GoTriple indexes and the graphs of the GoTriple KG.

4.5. Persistent Identifiers management

The implementation of a robust and consistent Persistent Identifier (PID) strategy is fundamental for ensuring that all resources managed by both GoTriple and the GoTriple KG, whether harvested, created, or semantically enriched, can be

persistently and unambiguously referenced. One of the FAIR requirements is in fact that “(meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier”³⁷.

GoTriple at present doesn't have a robust PID policy. In fact in GoTriple a PID consists of the URL of the presentation page of an entity. This URL is created by merging GoTriple's domain name with the original identifier of the content from the remote source, usually the first one returned during the harvesting phase, e.g.:

https://www.gotriple.eu/documents/<PRIMARY_ID> .

For example, the PID of a GoTriple document is:

<https://www.gotriple.eu/documents/oai%3Arevues.org%3Abergsoniana%2F1748> .

In general, using URLs for IDs is a bad idea. Some research³⁸ mentions that over a long period, a significant percentage of URLs (over 50%) become inaccessible. Also, linking an external identifier so strictly to GoTriple's ID is risky. In fact, when harvesting sources, it is common to receive multiple IDs for the same resource and the first one taken is not always the one intended to be persistent. It might be an internal ID that can change over time, provided that, if present, the persistent ID (e.g. a DOI) is maintained.

At the same time we need PIDs for identifying the entities of the GoTriple KG, so it has been decided to define a final strategy to be applied for both services, albeit with different methods.

To fix GoTriple's issues, it was considered at first a methodology inspired by the principles defined in the OpenAIRE Graph PID and Identifier Strategy³⁹: this way each GoTriple record can be assigned a persistent identifier generated according to the following pattern:

`<prefix>/sourceId_<md5(externalID)>`

³⁷ See: European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Aronsen, J., Beyan, O., Harrower, N. et al. (2021) *Recommendations on FAIR metrics for EOSC*. Publications Office. doi: 10.2777/70791.

³⁸ See for example: Stojanovski, J. *PIDs in the SSH - Current state and upcoming challenges*. TRIPLE Booksprint - The role of open metadata in the SSH scholarly communication, Konstancin-Jeziorna (Poland), 7-9 September 2022

³⁹ <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/data-model/pids-and-identifiers/>

where:

- prefix is the class of the content (document, dataset, profile, project...)
- sourceid is a 2 characters code that denotes the source of the record (e.g. oa for OpenAIRE, bn for Biblioteka Nauki, dj for DOAJ, etc.);
- md5 is used to generate a consistent, collision-resistant hash that ensures uniqueness even when different sources share overlapping IDs.

This identifier will be resolvable through stable HTTPS URLs structured as follows:

```
https://gotriple.eu/{PID}
```

where:

- PID is the internal GoTriple PID described above.

It can be also identified as got:{pid}

Examples:

- https://gotriple.eu/document/oa_d41d8cd98f00b204e9800998ecf8427e
 - got:document/oa_d41d8cd98f00b204e9800998ecf8427e
- https://gotriple.eu/dataset/dj_9b74c9897bac770ffc029102a200c5de
 - got:dataset/dj_9b74c9897bac770ffc029102a200c5de

After a further analysis with the project team, this strategy has been discarded. Several flaws have been identified, including:

- linking too strictly the PID with a URL can be risky as there is no guarantee that GoTriple's web address won't change in the future
- the resulting identifier is not compact as a PID should be
- the risk of having duplicates, albeit very low, cannot be excluded if the external source decide to reuse its internal ID to identify a different resource
- the resulting identifier is not a standard and recognised PID.

To avoid all these flaws it has been proposed to use the Archival Resource Key (ARK)⁴⁰, which is a well known and established PID service. It was introduced in 2001 and has shown a steady growth over time: its web site declares that 5 new ARK organizations are registered every week while it is estimated that over 15.3 billion ARKs have been generated so far.

⁴⁰ <https://arks.org/>

The structure of an ARK PID is:

```
ark:{NAAN}/{Assigned name}/{Sub-parts + Variants}
```

where:

- NAAN: is the Name Assigning Authority Number, which identifies the organisation. There must be a specific NAAN for GoTriple
- Assigned name, which is a unique identifier of the resource within the organisation
- Sub-parts + variants, that are optional identifiers, defined by the organisation to specify hierarchical subcomponents of the resource or its possible variants like versions, languages, or formats.

ARK presents significant advantages over alternative methodologies: first of all it is completely free, unlike the DOI or handle.net. Also, once a NAAN has been assigned, the organisation is entirely independent to produce PIDs, without the need to update a central service (unlike handle.net).

The only point of attention in GoTriple would be to define an effective strategy to produce short, and possibly self-explaining assigned names, for example, dXXXXXX for documents, pXXXXXX for projects, aXXXXXX for author profiles, tXXXXXX for datasets, sXXXXXX for semantic artefacts, and mXXXXXX for media objects, and where XXXXXX is a unique alphanumeric code within the index of the specific content type.

Finally, ARK has its own free name resolver service, Name-to-Thing (N2T)⁴¹. It allows valid ARK PIDs to be resolved and redirected to their actual web location.

This way, a GoTriple PID based on ARK will be something like:

Examples:

- <https://n2t.net/ark:<GoTripleNAAN>/dXXXXXX>
 - <ark:<GoTripleNAAN>/dXXXXXX>
- redirected to <https://gotriple.eu/document/dXXXXXX>

Finally, the URLs of the old GoTriple pages should be automatically redirected to the new URLs compliant to this PID methodology.

⁴¹ <http://n2t.net/>

For entities managed within the GoTriple KG, a distinct strategy will be adopted, taking inspiration from the European Data Portal’s “Design and Manage Persistent URIs” guidelines⁴².

In this context, URIs act as Persistent Identifiers for both real-world entities and conceptual resources described in the Knowledge Graph.

The GoTriple KG will follow a generic URI pattern structured as:

```
https://{domain}/{type}/{concept}/{reference}
```

where:

- {domain} can be either an internal URL, e.g. kg.gotriple.eu, or a persistent URL managed by the w3id.org service. In the latter case the domain will also include a unique “Identifier” for the GoTriple KG, e.g. https://w3id.org/got
- {type} is the category of the resource, chosen from a controlled list of short codes that declare its nature, such as: id or item for real-world entities (e.g. persons, organisations, projects), doc for documents describing those entities, def for concepts or terms (e.g. from controlled vocabularies or ontologies), set for datasets, etc.
- {concept} for indicating the type or class of the entity (e.g. publication, dataset, person, organisation, place, conceptScheme);
- {reference} is a local identifier, label, or hash corresponding to the specific entity.

The choice of w3id.org would be in line with the current practices in the semantic web and KG world. It allows the creation of fully dereferenceable and persistent URIs.

It can be considered a successor of the purl.org service, whose migration from the Online Computer Library Center (OCLC) to the Internet Archive in 2016 caused significant disruption and long-lasting problems to the community.

W3id.org is also backed by the W3C, which is an additional guarantee of its durability and stability: it is also the service used by OpenCitations for managing the URIs of its resources.

⁴²

https://data.europa.eu/sites/default/files/d2.1.2_training_module_2.3_persistent_uri_design_and_management_en_edp.pdf

Example URIs:

- <https://kg.gotriple.eu/id/person/0001a2b3> or <https://w3id.org/got/id/person/0001a2b3>
- <https://kg.gotriple.eu/doc/publication/10.1234-abc123> or <https://w3id.org/got/doc/publication/10.1234-abc123>
- <https://kg.gotriple.eu/def/concept/open-science> or <https://w3id.org/got/def/concept/open-science>
- <https://kg.gotriple.eu/set/dataset/graphia-survey-2025> or <https://w3id.org/got/set/dataset/graphia-survey-2025>

This model ensures semantic clarity, machine-actionable resolvability, and context-independent persistence, allowing URIs to serve both as identifiers and as dereferenceable resources within the federated SSH KG.

Each URI will resolve to a content-negotiated resource (e.g. HTML, RDF, JSON-LD), enabling human and machine access and supporting FAIR and Linked Open Data interoperability.

5. GoTriple KG Development and Deployment Infrastructure

5.1. Purpose of the GoTriple KG: from LPG to RDF

5.1.1. Context and strategic objectives

GRAPHIA has been designed as a technically ambitious project, aiming to build a next-generation knowledge graph infrastructure for the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). From the outset, the project envisioned a hybrid architecture combining RDF (Resource Description Framework) and LPG (Labelled Property Graph) technologies. This hybridisation was not an afterthought, but a strategic choice, intended to support three core technical objectives:

- Performance and scalability, to support large and complex graphs across distributed infrastructures;
- Advanced graph analytics, including topological queries such as shortest paths, centrality, and structural patterns;
- Graph data science, such as machine learning pipelines using graph embeddings and structural features.

Figure 5.1 – Initial hybrid architecture concept

This architecture responded to the dual reality of SSH research infrastructures: the need to maintain rich, semantically interoperable data (often RDF-based), while also enabling new forms of computational analysis and AI-driven discovery.

Hybridisation was therefore seen as a key enabler of GRAPHIA's mission: to reconcile semantic rigour with analytical innovation, and to serve a diverse landscape of users, from data providers to developers of intelligent services.

However, this ambition raised a number of architectural and strategic questions:

- How can RDF and LPG coexist within a coherent, modular architecture?
- What are the trade-offs between maintaining a semantically grounded core and enabling high-performance analytics?
- To what extent should hybridisation be embedded in the core infrastructure versus delegated to dedicated modules?
- How can we ensure long-term sustainability, FAIR compliance, and clarity of governance across the technical components?

These questions did not challenge the relevance of hybridisation itself, on the contrary, they reaffirmed its importance. But they also highlighted the need for a structured, criteria-based assessment of how hybridisation could best be implemented within GRAPHIA's ecosystem, timeline, and distributed governance model.

5.1.2. Evaluation criteria

To support a structured and transparent architectural decision, the GRAPHIA team defined a common evaluation framework to compare possible hybridisation strategies. This framework is based on 9 objective criteria, grouped into three overarching categories:

1. *Strategic and Ecosystem Alignment*, assessing compatibility with the project vision, ecosystem, and user needs;
2. *Technical Feasibility and Sustainability*, evaluating the architecture's modularity, complexity, and maintainability;
3. *Performance, Operations and Deployment*, focusing on real-world performance, interoperability, and ease of implementation.

Each scenario was assessed using a three-level score scale:

- 1 = Low alignment (major concerns or poor fit)
- 2 = Moderate alignment (partially meets expectations, with limitations)

- 3 = High alignment (fully meets the criterion, no major issues)

This framework was not designed to mechanically “select a winner”, but to highlight trade-offs, surface tensions, and support informed architectural deliberation across partners.

Category	Criterion	Guiding Question
1. Strategic & Ecosystem Alignment	1.1 Ecosystem Compatibility	Does the approach align with RDF-centric infrastructures and practices?
	1.2 Use Case Relevance	Does it respond directly to the needs identified in WP3, WP4, and WP5?
	1.3 Innovation Deliverability	Can the project realistically deliver on its hybridisation ambition?
2. Technical Feasibility & Sustainability	2.1 Modularity and Decoupling	Can components be separated to limit risk and improve flexibility?
	2.2 Implementation Complexity	What technical effort is required to implement and maintain the approach?
	2.3 Maintainability	Can the architecture be sustained beyond the project’s lifespan?
3. Performance, Operations & Deployment	3.1 Performance on Target Workloads	Can it support reasoning, analytics, and graph operations at scale?
	3.2 FAIR Interoperability	Does the solution preserve semantic richness, federation, and provenance?
	3.3 Deployment Simplicity	Is the solution easy to deploy, operate, and scale across partners?

Table 5.1 – Summary of evaluation criteria

5.1.3. Explored scenarios

To translate the hybridisation ambition of GRAPHIA into concrete architectural choices, the team explored a set of four plausible scenarios, discussed in depth across WP2 and assessed against the evaluation criteria outlined above. Each scenario reflects a distinct philosophy of how RDF and LPG technologies could interact within the project's ecosystem.

The scenarios differ in the degree of integration between RDF and LPG, the location of the LPG component (core vs. peripheral), and the impact on the semantic backbone of the infrastructure:

- **Scenario A - RDF + LPG Coexistence:** this scenario envisions a parallel architecture where an RDF triple store (e.g., GraphDB, Virtuoso) serves as the semantic core, while a separate LPG engine (e.g., Neo4j) handles traversal and analytics. Synchronisation pipelines ensure consistency between the two layers.
 - Example: Neo4j + RDF sync via neosemantics (n10s) plugin.
- **Scenario B - RDF Triple Store Only:** this approach focuses entirely on RDF technologies, leveraging recent advances such as RDF-star, federation, and reasoning optimisations. Graph analytics are addressed through RDF-native extensions or deprioritised.
 - Example: GraphDB v11, QLever, or Stardog with RDF-star.
- **Scenario C - LPG-Only with RDF Plugin:** this scenario flips the stack: LPG becomes the core, with RDF support layered in via plugins (e.g., Neo4j's n10s). RDF is mapped into LPG-native structures for querying.
 - Example: Neo4j + n10s.
- **Scenario D - RDF Core + LPG as External AI/Analytics Module:** here, LPG is treated as an optional, isolated component for advanced graph analytics, operating on specific RDF subgraphs without altering the core. It is activated on demand (e.g., for WP4 experimentation) and does not affect the semantic backbone.
 - Example: GRAPHIA Task 4.3 LPG prototype module.
- **Excluded Scenarios:** several options were deliberately excluded from the evaluation due to critical limitations:

- Natively hybrid or closed platforms (e.g., Neptune, AnzoGraph) due to vendor lock-in, opaque logic, or licence constraints.
- LPG-only without RDF capabilities, incompatible with the project’s semantic goals.
- Deeply entangled RDF-LPG architectures, which risk blurring governance boundaries and increasing complexity without added functional clarity.

5.1.4. Comparative assessment

Building on the context (5.1.1), evaluation criteria (5.1.2), and explored scenarios (5.1.3), we conducted a comparative assessment of each option using a common 1–3 scoring scale. This evaluation clarifies the trade-offs between innovation, feasibility, and ecosystem alignment, without preempting a final choice. The results highlight how each scenario performs across key dimensions and inform the architectural direction of GRAPHIA.

Scenario A – RDF + LPG Coexistence

Category	Criterion	Score	Explanations
1. Strategic & Ecosystem Alignment	1.1 Ecosystem compatibility	2	While RDF is natively compatible with the ecosystem, introducing a parallel LPG layer adds complexity and deviates from common practice in the academic LOD/FAIR ecosystem.
	1.2 Use Case relevance	2	Some advanced analytical use cases may benefit from LPG, but current WP3/WP4/WP5 inputs do not reveal critical needs requiring real-time traversal or graph algorithms.
	1.3 Innovation Deliverability	3	This scenario maximally satisfies the hybridisation promise in its original form, fulfilling the innovation commitment made in the DoA.
2. Technical Feasibility & Sustainability	2.1 Modularity and decoupling	2	RDF and LPG can technically be decoupled, but this requires a well-maintained replication pipeline. Governance and data consistency across layers remain a concern.
	2.2 Implementation complexity	1	Dual-stack architectures are complex to implement, especially with synchronisation needs, query translations, and potential semantic drift between models.
	2.3 Maintainability	1	Maintaining two graph engines with different paradigms implies long-term technical debt, higher expertise requirements, and a greater risk of divergence.
3. Performance, Operations & Deployment	3.1 Performance on target workloads	3	Very strong performance for LPG-side analytics, assuming graph traversal and algorithmic use cases emerge. RDF layer remains performant for semantic querying.
	3.2 FAIR interoperability	2	The RDF layer ensures strong FAIR alignment. However, the LPG side introduces risks (e.g. lack of standard RDF exports unless reprojected).
	3.3 Deployment simplicity	1	Deploying, integrating, and operating two separate engines increases the operational burden, especially for smaller partners or decentralised setups.

Figure 5.2 – Scenario A assessment

This scenario scores well on innovation deliverability and analytical performance, clearly fulfilling the original hybridisation ambition of GRAPHIA. However, the evaluation reveals major concerns in terms of implementation complexity, long-term

maintainability, and deployment overhead - especially in distributed, multi-partner environments.

Although RDF and LPG layers can be technically decoupled, they require synchronisation workflows, replication pipelines, and consistent governance practices. These factors introduce technical debt, increase operational risks, and may challenge sustainability and FAIR alignment.

The scenario's trade-off is clear: maximum innovation impact, but significant complexity and cost in terms of maintenance, governance, and ecosystem compatibility.

Scenario B - RDF Triple Store Only

Category	Criterion	Score	Explanations
1. Strategic & Ecosystem Alignment	1.1 Ecosystem compatibility	3	Fully aligned with the academic and Linked Open Data ecosystem; RDF is already the reference in FAIR, semantic web, and EOSC-related infrastructures.
	1.2 Use Case relevance	2	Most current use cases (WP3/WP4/WP5) are compatible with RDF; however, potential for future advanced analytics is limited without LPG.
	1.3 Innovation Deliverability	1	This scenario fails to deliver on the hybridisation innovation promised in the proposal unless complemented by alternative modules or justifications.
2. Technical Feasibility & Sustainability	2.1 Modularity and decoupling	3	A single-model RDF architecture offers high modularity and clear governance structure, simplifying responsibilities and component evolution.
	2.2 Implementation complexity	3	Technically simple to implement; existing triple stores (e.g. GraphDB, Virtuoso) are mature and well-documented, with minimal integration overhead.
	2.3 Maintainability	3	Easy to maintain long-term, due to standardisation, community support, and consistency across deployments. No need for synchronisation pipelines.
3. Performance, Operations & Deployment	3.1 Performance on target workloads	2	RDF triple stores are performant on semantic queries and scalable on large datasets (GraphDB v11, QLever), but not optimised for graph analytics (even with RDF*/SPARQL*)
	3.2 FAIR interoperability	3	Full support for semantic interoperability, provenance, and metadata alignment. Strong adherence to FAIR principles.
	3.3 Deployment simplicity	3	Very easy to deploy across partners; RDF infrastructure is lightweight, mature, and requires fewer operational resources than hybrid stacks

Figure 5.3 – Scenario B assessment

This scenario offers maximum compatibility with existing infrastructures, strong FAIR compliance, and excellent maintainability. Its simplicity makes it attractive for deployment and governance, with limited technical overhead. However, it only partially meets the hybridisation promise of the DoA, unless complemented by external components to support advanced analytics. Its main trade-off lies in sacrificing LPG-native capabilities to favour stability and interoperability, positioning it as a conservative but robust option.

Scenario C - LPG-Only with RDF Plugin

Category	Criterion	Score	Explanations
1. Strategic & Ecosystem Alignment	1.1 Ecosystem compatibility	1	LPG-first architectures are not native to the Linked Open Data ecosystem and require custom tooling (e.g., n10s) to simulate RDF semantics. Limited alignment with current academic infrastructures.
	1.2 Use Case relevance	2	The model supports advanced analytics and traversal, which could be useful in the long term. However, these needs are not currently expressed as priorities in WP3/WP4.
	1.3 Innovation Deliverability	2	This scenario technically supports hybridisation via plugin-based RDF exposure, but the RDF layer is secondary and lacks full standards compliance (e.g., limited SPARQL support).
2. Technical Feasibility & Sustainability	2.1 Modularity and decoupling	1	RDF capabilities are tightly coupled to the LPG core. This blurs roles and makes semantic governance harder to isolate or delegate.
	2.2 Implementation complexity	2	Neo4j with n10s is relatively easy to install, but RDF integration remains partial and may require custom mappings and frequent updates.
	2.3 Maintainability	1	Long-term maintenance of RDF compatibility depends on a plugin outside of W3C standards. Potential drift from expected FAIR practices over time.
3. Performance, Operations & Deployment	3.1 Performance on target workloads	3	Excellent performance for graph analytics, pattern detection, and traversal queries, provided those use cases become relevant.
	3.2 FAIR interoperability	1	FAIR compliance is limited. RDF is emulated, not native, and semantic inference, reusability, or federated querying are constrained.
	3.3 Deployment simplicity	2	Neo4j is easy to deploy, but requires additional configuration for RDF import/export, and technical familiarity that may not be shared across the consortium.

Figure 5.4 – Scenario C assessment

This scenario offers high performance for analytics, especially graph traversal and pattern detection, but relies on plugin-based RDF emulation, which limits semantic interoperability and FAIR compliance. Governance and decoupling are weaker, as RDF logic is tightly embedded in the LPG core.

While technically feasible, the approach introduces long-term risks of misalignment with open standards and ecosystem expectations. It may suit advanced analytics, but remains a non-native fit for FAIR-centric infrastructures.

Scenario D - RDF Core + LPG as External AI/Analytics Module

Category	Criterion	Score	Explanations
1. Strategic & Ecosystem Alignment	1.1 Ecosystem compatibility	3	Fully compatible with the RDF-centric landscape of academic infrastructures, while keeping LPG decoupled enough to avoid disrupting interoperability principles.
	1.2 Use Case relevance	2	Current needs don't require native LPG integration, but this approach keeps the door open for targeted analytics where relevant (e.g., Task 4.3).
	1.3 Innovation Deliverability	3	The hybridisation objective is addressed through a dedicated AI/analytics module operating on RDF subgraphs. While this component is not part of the core architecture, it offers a concrete and demonstrable implementation of hybrid features in a scoped, low-risk environment.
2. Technical Feasibility & Sustainability	2.1 Modularity and decoupling	3	The LPG component is cleanly separated, reducing dependencies and allowing for controlled evolution and prototyping.
	2.2 Implementation complexity	2	Requires some effort to set up a data projection pipeline from RDF to LPG for analytical use, but avoids complications of full hybrid integration.
	2.3 Maintainability	3	Clear separation of concerns simplifies long-term maintenance and avoids spreading technical debt across the entire stack.
3. Performance, Operations & Deployment	3.1 Performance on target workloads	3	Offers high performance for analytics through LPG, without compromising the core RDF infrastructure's stability or scalability.
	3.2 FAIR interoperability	3	FAIR compliance is preserved in the core RDF layer, while LPG remains isolated and does not interfere with semantic governance.
	3.3 Deployment simplicity	2	Slightly more complex than RDF-only, as it involves maintaining an external module, but significantly simpler than full hybrid or coexistence models.

Figure 5.5 – Scenario D assessment

This modular scenario delivers on the hybridisation objective without entangling the core architecture. The RDF backbone remains fully aligned with FAIR and EOSC standards, while LPG is leveraged only where needed, for specific analytics. The decoupling ensures maintainability, low implementation risk, and preserves governance clarity. Although it involves a lightweight data transformation process (to map specific RDF subgraphs into LPG structures), this option offers a strategic balance between innovation and long-term sustainability.

5.1.5. Decision

Following a comparative analysis of the four scenarios, **Scenario D – RDF Core + LPG as an external AI module clearly emerges as the most balanced and sustainable option**. It achieves the highest overall score (24/27), combining ecosystem alignment, technical feasibility, and operational simplicity, while still addressing the innovation goals set out in the DoA.

Category	Criterion	A. RDF + LPG Coexistence	B. RDF Triple Store Only	C. LPG-Only with RDF Plugin	D. RDF Core + LPG as AI module
1. Strategic & Ecosystem Alignment	1.1 Ecosystem compatibility	2	3	1	3
	1.2 Use Case relevance	2	2	2	2
	1.3 Innovation Deliverability	3	1	2	3
2. Technical Feasibility & Sustainability	2.1 Modularity and decoupling	2	3	1	3
	2.2 Implementation complexity	1	3	2	2
	2.3 Maintainability	1	3	1	3
3. Performance, Operations & Deployment	3.1 Performance on target workloads	3	2	3	3
	3.2 FAIR interoperability	2	3	1	3
	3.3 Deployment simplicity	1	3	2	2
	TOTAL	17	23	15	24

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Figure 5.6 – Comparison of evaluations

This option preserves the FAIR-native RDF architecture as the core, fully compatible with EOSC infrastructures and Linked Open Data practices, while introducing LPG-based analytics in a controlled, decoupled manner. It delivers the hybridisation promise through a dedicated module (e.g., for GRAPHIA Task 4.3), without burdening the platform with dual-stack complexity or long-term technical debt.

Importantly, this does not represent a renunciation of hybridisation, but a strategic reframing: hybridisation is maintained, but through modular decoupling, ensuring robustness, maintainability, and agility for future extensions.

This decision aligns with the project’s innovation commitments, while ensuring a pragmatic path forward for implementation.

5.1.6. Architectural implications and module boundaries

The selected architecture establishes RDF as the authoritative knowledge graph layer, ensuring full alignment with FAIR principles, semantic web standards, and EOSC-compatible infrastructures. All data modelling, querying, and governance functions remain within this core layer.

The LPG component is isolated within a dedicated AI/analytics module, downstream of the RDF layer. It operates on projected subgraphs, with no upstream write-back, avoiding any interference with the core ontology or governance logic. This separation:

- Preserves modularity and maintainability;
- Enables targeted, experimental use of LPG (e.g. pattern mining, embeddings);
- Avoids the burden of dual infrastructure governance.

A transformation pipeline from RDF to LPG will serve as a reusable, FAIR-aligned interface, ensuring transparency and traceability.

Implications for WP4 - T4.3

T4.3 is expected to prototype AI modules using LPG technologies (e.g. Neo4j) for enrichment or discovery tasks. These modules must:

- Remain clearly decoupled from the RDF core;
- Be treated as optional consumers, not as authoritative stores;
- Respect the modular architecture and semantic boundaries;
- Define explicit integration points and data flows with RDF components.

The first phase of T4.3 should focus on minimal, high-impact use cases where LPG-specific capabilities (e.g. path queries, structural patterns, embeddings) can support SSH-related discovery or enrichment.

Critically, T4.3 is not responsible for maintaining a parallel knowledge graph infrastructure: the LPG layer is a functional extension, not a second graph core.

5.1.7. Key considerations

The selected architecture offers a balanced path: it honours GRAPHIA's commitment to a FAIR, RDF-native infrastructure, while opening space for innovation through a decoupled LPG-based AI module. This approach delivers on the hybridisation promise, yet it introduces a number of strategic and operational risks that require careful framing:

- **Strategic positioning** remains critical. If not clearly articulated, the inclusion of LPG technologies, even as an optional module, could be perceived as a

deviation from the initial proposal. To prevent this, the LPG layer must be presented as experimental, complementary, and fully aligned with the RDF-first vision of the platform.

- **Architectural clarity** must also be preserved. The RDF backbone is the sole authoritative infrastructure. Any LPG-based processing must remain downstream, non-intrusive, and explicitly framed as non-core. Confusion here could lead to misinterpretation of the project's compliance and scope.
- **Sustainability** depends on strict modularity. The LPG module must remain focused on targeted analytics, graph embeddings, structural patterns, path queries—without attempting to replicate or override RDF functionalities. Without such boundaries, the risk of technical drift and long-term maintenance overhead increases sharply.
- **Cross-work package coordination and effort alignment** will be essential to ensure coherence. While the module is developed within WP4 (T4.3), it depends on data and architecture managed by WP2. Without clear boundaries and shared understanding of roles and dependencies, misalignments may arise. Given the engineering complexity involved—data projection, AI integration, lifecycle handling, effort allocation should be reviewed to ensure feasibility within existing commitments.

5.2. The technology behind the GoTriple KG

5.2.1. Context and strategic objectives

The definition of the RDF core engine is a cornerstone of GRAPHIA's technical architecture. As outlined in the original proposal, this component must ensure interoperability, reasoning, and FAIR data integration through shared ontologies and SPARQL queries. It must also scale with the evolving demands of a distributed, research-intensive ecosystem.

Figure 5.7 – Initial GRAPHIA RDF core engine

The strategic objective was to identify a triple store capable of supporting GRAPHIA's semantic backbone with robustness, openness, and sustainability. Beyond basic compliance with RDF standards, the solution had to align with community-driven governance principles (Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure - POSI), enable long-term maintainability, and support modular integration with complementary technologies such as LPG.

The selection process therefore combined three layers of analysis:

- A review of the current state of the art, focusing on SPARQL capabilities, scalability, and maturity;
- A synthesis of usage needs across work packages, particularly WP3, WP4 and WP5;
- An internal validation process, including partner feedback and a dedicated RDF Technologies workshop.

This section summarises the outcomes of this selection process, leading to the adoption of Virtuoso as the RDF core engine and the optional consideration of QLever as a lightweight analytical backend.

5.2.2. Evaluation criteria

To ensure a transparent and balanced decision, a shared evaluation framework was defined across WP2 partners. It includes 12 objective criteria, structured along four thematic pillars:

- *Core Feature Coverage*: RDF 1.1/SPARQL support, reasoning, federated querying;
- *Scalability & Performance*: query execution, ingestion pipelines, clustering models;
- *Usability & Deployability*: ease of setup, ecosystem maturity, monitoring tools;
- *Strategic Fit*: open-source compliance, FAIR alignment, long-term sustainability.

Each scenario was assessed using a three-level score scale:

- 1 = Low alignment (major concerns or poor fit)
- 2 = Moderate alignment (partially meets expectations, with limitations)
- 3 = High alignment (fully meets the criterion, no major issues)

Category	Criterion	Guiding Question
1. Core Feature Coverage	1.1 RDF and SPARQL compliance	Does the approach align with RDF-centric infrastructures and practices?
	1.2 Reasoning capabilities	Does it respond directly to the needs identified in WP3, WP4, and WP5?
	1.3 Federated querying and data linking	Can the project realistically deliver on its hybridisation ambition?
2. Scalability & Performance	2.1 Query performance on large datasets	Can components be separated to limit risk and improve flexibility?
	2.2 Data ingestion & indexing scalability	What technical effort is required to implement and maintain the approach?

	2.3 Clustering and distribution model	Can the architecture be sustained beyond the project's lifespan?
3. Usability & Deployability	3.1 Ease of deployment and documentation	Can it support reasoning, analytics, and graph operations at scale?
	3.2 Maturity and ecosystem support	Does the solution preserve semantic richness, federation, and provenance?
	3.3 Monitoring and administration tools	Is the solution easy to deploy, operate, and scale across partners?
4. Strategic Fit	4.1 Open-source compliance and licensing	Is the engine fully open-source with a permissive license? Are advanced features freely available?
	4.2 Long-term sustainability	Is the engine under active development? Is there a clear roadmap, and is the project backed by a sustainable institution or community?
	4.3 Interoperability and FAIR alignment	Does the engine align with FAIR principles (e.g., use of open vocabularies, standards like DCAT, schema.org)? Is it compatible with EOSC-oriented infrastructures?

Table 5.2 – Detailed evaluation criteria

5.2.3. Identified solutions

Three viable RDF engine configurations were shortlisted, each offering a credible path to support the semantic backbone of GRAPHIA:

- **Solution A - GraphDB:** Feature-rich and widely adopted in FAIR infrastructures, GraphDB excels in reasoning and SPARQL federation. However, its proprietary license and limited transparency were key concerns.

- **Solution B - QLever:** This lightweight engine delivers exceptional SPARQL performance on large datasets with a small footprint. While named graph support has been introduced since our initial assessment (reflecting the engine's rapid evolution) its ecosystem is currently less consolidated for a full-stack deployment compared to long-standing alternatives.
- **Solution C - Virtuoso:** Combining SPARQL, SQL, and federated querying, Virtuoso offers a balanced and proven architecture. Despite a steeper learning curve, its open-source model and operational maturity tipped the scale in its favor.

Several other engines (e.g., Stardog, AllegroGraph, Blazegraph, TerminusDB) were excluded due to licensing constraints, FAIR misalignment, or insufficient maturity.

5.2.4. Comparative assessment

Building on the strategic context (5.2.1), evaluation criteria (5.2.2), and identified solutions (5.2.3), we conducted a comparative assessment of the shortlisted RDF engines using a unified 1–3 scoring scale.

This evaluation clarifies the trade-offs between feature completeness, performance, and strategic alignment, without pre-empting a binary choice.

The results highlight how each solution performs across key dimensions - informing the final adoption of Virtuoso as the RDF core engine, complemented by QLever under a feasibility study.

Solution A - GraphDB

Category	Criterion	Score	Explanations
1. Core Feature Coverage	1.1 RDF and SPARQL compliance	3	Fully supports RDF 1.1 and SPARQL 1.1 (including named graphs). Notably, GraphDB has implemented the upcoming RDF-star extension, allowing statements about statements. It uses the triple-quoting RDF-star syntax with optimized storage, nearly doubling load speed for metadata-rich datasets.
	1.2 Reasoning capabilities	3	Strong built-in rule-based inference engine. GraphDB (formerly OWLIM) performs RDFS and OWL reasoning (OWL Horst/DLP profiles and up to OWL 2 RL/QL) via its TRREE engine. It supports configurable rulesets (RDFS, OWL2-RL, OWL2-QL, etc.) and can materialize inferences eagerly. While it doesn't cover the full OWL 2 DL (no complex class axioms beyond RL), it provides "full standard-compliant reasoning" for the major profiles, which is comprehensive among triple stores.
	1.3 Federated querying and data linking	3	Supports SPARQL 1.1 Federated Query (SERVICE) for remote endpoints out-of-the-box. GraphDB's SPARQL engine treats SERVICE as a subquery and can perform standard federated queries (e.g. joining with DBpedia endpoints). It also integrates with the FedX federation layer to query multiple repositories or endpoints efficiently.
2. Scalability & Performance	2.1 Query performance on large datasets	2	GraphDB exhibits decent query performance at scale, but it is not the fastest engine in this group. In independent Wikidata benchmarks, GraphDB trailed top performers like Virtuoso in query speed. For example, on a 390M triple dataset (DBLP), GraphDB achieved ~16s average query time, slower than Virtuoso (~2.2s) and QLever (~0.7s) under similar conditions (wikidata.org).
	2.2 Data ingestion & indexing scalability	2	Capable of handling billions of triples, though import speeds and index size are moderate. GraphDB supports bulk loading and parallel import, but in tests it loaded RDF at ~0.4 million triples/second, slower than QLever's custom indexer. Its indexed footprint (e.g. ~28 GB for 390M triples) was mid-range (wikidata.org). Still, GraphDB's storage engine scales to large graphs; v11 improved RDF-star storage and supports external index synchronization.
	2.3 Clustering and distribution model	2	Only with enterprise features. Offers high-availability clustering via master-slave replication (enterprise edition). A GraphDB cluster keeps full copies on multiple nodes for fault tolerance and read scaling. However, it does not support sharding or true horizontal partitioning of data – all cluster nodes must hold all data. This replication approach provides HA and load balancing but cannot distribute a single huge dataset across nodes. Since sharding is not implemented, GraphDB's horizontal scaling is limited (enterprise-only feature with quorum-based replication).
3. Usability & Deployability	3.1 Ease of deployment and documentation	2	Moderately easy to deploy. Ontotext provides comprehensive documentation and a web-based Workbench UI for GraphDB. Docker images and a Helm chart are available for containerized deployment. However, usage of GraphDB Free requires obtaining a (free) license key, which adds a step. Overall setup is straightforward, but not completely frictionless, a user evaluation noted "some hurdles" in getting GraphDB running.
	3.2 Maturity and ecosystem support	3	Very mature product with a long history (initial release in 2002). GraphDB is an enterprise-grade engine used in many production systems and backed by Ontotext, which ensures regular releases (v11 introduced major features like GraphQL integration). A rich ecosystem surrounds it: it's compatible with RDF4J, has connectors for full-text search, and a community of users in industry and academia. The longevity and active maintenance (over two decades) demonstrate strong maturity and institutional backing.
	3.3 Monitoring and administration tools	2	Provides basic but useful admin tools. The GraphDB Workbench offers a GUI to manage repositories, load data, and run SPARQL queries. It also exposes some metrics (query logs, slow query monitoring) and supports Java JMX for deeper monitoring. However, it lacks out-of-the-box integration with modern monitoring stacks (no built-in Prometheus exporter) and has limited real-time query profiling compared to RDBMS systems. Administration is user-friendly via the UI, but low-level monitoring and performance tuning require manual effort or third-party tools.
4. Strategic Fit	4.1 Open-source compliance and licensing	1	Not fully open-source. GraphDB is a commercial product; the "GraphDB Free" edition is free to use (even for non-commercial use) but requires a license from Ontotext and does not expose source code. Core features like clustering or advanced analytics are part of the Enterprise Edition. While GraphDB adheres to open standards, its code and some capabilities are proprietary (enterprise-gated). This restrictive licensing and lack of a permissive OSS license give it a low score on open-source compliance.
	4.2 Long-term sustainability	3	High confidence in sustainability. GraphDB's development is backed by Ontotext (an established semantic technology company) with an active roadmap and funding. The product has seen continuous improvements (e.g., GraphDB 10 and 11 releases with new features) and regular maintenance. Its widespread adoption in enterprise knowledge graph projects and governmental data portals ensures continued support. With a dedicated company and user base behind it, GraphDB is likely to remain well-supported in the long term.
	4.3 Interoperability and FAIR alignment	2	Aligns well with FAIR data principles through its support of W3C standards, but provides few out-of-the-box features specifically for FAIR publishing. GraphDB stores data in RDF and offers SPARQL endpoints, which makes data Findable and Accessible to semantic tools. It can be used in Linked Open Data scenarios (serving as the backend for data catalogs or LOD datasets) and supports vocabularies like RDF Schema and OWL for Interoperability. However, GraphDB itself does not automatically publish dataset metadata (no built-in DCAT catalog) or content negotiation for IRIs, those must be configured on top. It enables FAIR compliance, but the burden is on the implementation; hence only a moderate score.

Figure 5.8 – Solution A assessment

GraphDB offers a robust RDF backbone, with full support for SPARQL 1.1, reasoning profiles (RDFS, OWL2-RL/QL), and RDF-star extensions. It performs well in terms of semantic expressivity and is widely adopted in FAIR infrastructures. However, its performance on large-scale queries and bulk ingestion is moderate compared to other options. Clustering and horizontal scalability are limited to the enterprise edition, raising concerns about long-term openness and architectural flexibility.

GraphDB scores highly on maturity and sustainability, with a stable release cycle, strong commercial backing, and long-standing adoption in the community. Yet, its restrictive licensing model and partial open-source compliance represent major drawbacks, especially in the context of POSI aligned governance. Interoperability with FAIR publishing tools is solid, but not seamless, requiring additional configuration for metadata-rich use cases.

Solution B – Qlever

Category	Criterion	Score	Explanations
1. Core Feature Coverage	1.1 RDF and SPARQL compliance	2	Almost full SPARQL 1.1 support, with a few gaps. QLever's goal is to implement the entire SPARQL 1.1 spec, and it currently handles most query forms and functions. It also supports useful extensions like combined text search. However, as of the latest version, QLever does not support named graphs (it operates over a single default graph). SPARQL update is only a proof-of-concept, and some advanced features (e.g., certain query algebra corner cases) are still being finalized.
	1.2 Reasoning capabilities	1	No built-in reasoning or inference. QLever is designed as a SPARQL query engine optimized for speed and scale, and it does not perform RDFS/OWL entailment. It treats the data as-is, without any rule-based inference. There is no support for OWL reasoning or rule plugins in QLever. Users would need to materialize any required inferences beforehand using external tools.
	1.3 Federated querying and data linking	2	Partial support for federated queries. QLever recently introduced an initial implementation of the SPARQL SERVICE syntax for federated querying, allowing it to dispatch sub-queries to remote endpoints. This is a new feature (available since PR #793) and may still be experimental. Earlier, QLever had no federation ability. With the new update, it can perform basic federated queries, but the maturity and completeness (e.g., error handling, SERVICE joins optimization) are not yet on par with long-standing engines.
2. Scalability & Performance	2.1 Query performance on large datasets	3	Excellent performance at scale, especially for complex or heavy queries. QLever is built for very large knowledge graphs and excels in queries producing huge intermediate or final result sets. Empirical evaluations show QLever outperforming other engines in many cases: for instance, queries against the full Wikidata that timeout on other systems often run in under a second on QLever. Its custom indexing and query planner are optimized for join efficiency and can handle 100+ billion triples on a single server. QLever's ability to quickly deliver results for otherwise intractable queries (e.g., broad graph scans or large unions) demonstrates top-tier performance in this category.
	2.2 Data ingestion & indexing scalability	3	Highly scalable ingestion and efficient indexing. QLever's index construction is impressively fast and space-efficient. In a comparison on a 390M triple dataset, QLever built its index in only ~231 seconds (1.7M triples/sec) with an index size of ~9 GB, substantially faster and smaller than the other engines. It uses a compressed, sorted index structure (with permutations of SPO) that scales to tens of billions of triples on a single machine. Although indexing is a batch process (QLever is read-only after indexing, as SPARQL Update is experimental), the one-time ingestion scales very effectively. This makes QLever well-suited for very large static graphs.
	2.3 Clustering and distribution model	1	No horizontal scaling support. QLever is designed for a single-node deployment that leverages that node's full resources (CPU/RAM). It does not offer sharding or replication across multiple servers, instead, it aims to load an entire huge graph on one machine (the developers report handling 100B+ triples on one server). There is no built-in mechanism for a distributed QLever cluster or high-availability replication. If one needs more data than fits on one server, QLever has no native cluster solution (beyond possibly splitting data manually between separate QLever instances).
3. Usability & Deployability	3.1 Ease of deployment and documentation	3	Very easy to deploy and get started. QLever provides a Docker-based setup and a helper script (qlever script) that automates indexing and running the engine. This means users can spin up QLever without compiling from source, and the documentation (on the GitHub README and wiki) includes step-by-step guides. The project offers demo instances and example configurations, which lowers the barrier to entry.
	3.2 Maturity and ecosystem support	2	QLever is a relatively young project (initial release in 2017) and is primarily developed by a research team at University of Freiburg. It has made significant progress and is stable enough to power the official DBLP SPARQL endpoint. However, its community is still small compared to long-established triple stores. It doesn't have large corporate backing, though it's gaining interest (e.g., considered as a candidate for the Wikidata Query Service). The release cycle depends on academic funding and contributors.
	3.3 Monitoring and administration tools	1	Limited administration and monitoring facilities. QLever runs as a service with a SPARQL endpoint and basic web UI for queries (including context-sensitive auto-completion), but it lacks a dedicated admin interface or monitoring dashboard. There are no built-in tools for live query monitoring, user management, or performance metrics export.
4. Strategic Fit	4.1 Open-source compliance and licensing	3	QLever is fully open-source under a permissive Apache 2.0 license. All features of QLever are available in the open repository, with no enterprise-only extensions. This allows anyone to use, modify, or integrate QLever freely. Its Apache license and public GitHub development make it highly compliant with open-source principles.
	4.2 Long-term sustainability	2	The project shows active development and academic interest, but long-term support is somewhat less certain than for commercial products. On the positive side, QLever's core team has continued improving it and the engine's consideration by Wikidata indicates ongoing relevance. The multiple research papers and the fact it underpins some public endpoints reflect a commitment to its maintenance. However, as an academic project, its future depends on research grants or community uptake. There is no dedicated company guaranteeing its development indefinitely.
	4.3 Interoperability and FAIR alignment	2	QLever is built on open standards (if only speaks SPARQL and RDF), which ensures interoperability with other Semantic Web tools and adherence to the technical aspects of FAIR. It can readily consume and expose Linked Open Data: for example, it powers open SPARQL endpoints like for DBLP, making that data accessible and queryable (FAIR). However, QLever doesn't specifically provide features like content negotiation or vocabulary mapping on its own – it's essentially a high-performance SPARQL endpoint.

Figure 5.9 – Solution B assessment

QLever stands out for its remarkable SPARQL query performance and efficient indexing at a very large scale. Its compressed index structure enables low memory usage and fast retrieval, making it highly suitable for read-heavy workloads and static datasets. It also offers one of the best performances for complex queries on large graphs. However, it lacks full RDF support, including reasoning and named graphs, and its SPARQL compliance is still evolving.

Ease of deployment is a key strength: QLever is fully open-source, containerisable, and simple to run without complex setup. However, it is designed for single-node deployments and does not support clustering, replication, or high availability, limiting its scalability in a distributed architecture. Monitoring capabilities are also minimal, with no dedicated UI or built-in performance tracking tools.

Strategically, QLever aligns well with POSI-aligned governance thanks to its permissive license and transparent development process. Yet, its academic origins mean long-term sustainability is less assured than enterprise-backed alternatives. FAIR alignment is partial: while it supports SPARQL and open standards, it does not provide out-of-the-box support for linked metadata or interoperability mappings.

In summary, QLever is an impressive analytical engine with outstanding performance and openness, but its architectural and feature limitations prevent it from serving as GRAPHIA's primary RDF backbone.

Solution C - Virtuoso

Category	Criterion	Score	Explanations
1. Core Feature Coverage	1.1 RDF and SPARQL compliance	3	Virtuoso offers broad compliance with RDF 1.1 and SPARQL 1.1 query language and protocol. It supports all key SPARQL 1.1 features and uses a quad-store model to handle named graphs. One gap is RDF-star: as of now, Virtuoso does not support RDF*/SPARQL* (the team has taken a "wait until standard" stance). Since RDF-star isn't an official standard yet, this doesn't detract from Virtuoso's full compliance with current W3C standards, so it earns top marks.
	1.2 Reasoning capabilities	2	Provides basic inferencing, but not comprehensive OWL reasoning. Virtuoso can apply RDFS and a subset of OWL entailments at query time by using an "inference rule set" (ontology loaded into a rule context). It natively supports RDFS hierarchies (subClassOf/subPropertyOf) and simple equivalence or sameAs handling. For example, when a ruleset is enabled, Virtuoso will treat owl:equivalentClass or owl:sameAs links as equality, and infer subclass relationships accordingly. However, it does not support the full OWL 2 profile; complex OWL constructs beyond those (e.g., unionOf, intersectionOf) are not handled. No built-in description logic reasoner is present.
	1.3 Federated querying and data linking	3	Fully supports federated SPARQL queries. Virtuoso implements the SPARQL 1.1 SERVICE clause, allowing queries to include remote SPARQL endpoints and join results across them. This capability has been in Virtuoso for years and is used in distributed query scenarios. In practice, one can send part of a query to another endpoint (e.g., DBpedia's SPARQL) via SERVICE <endpoint> (...) and Virtuoso will retrieve and combine those results. Virtuoso's compliance with the SPARQL protocol also means it can serve as a federated source itself.
2. Scalability & Performance	2.1 Query performance on large datasets	3	Proven high performance on big graphs. Virtuoso has consistently shown strong query execution speeds and robust optimization, often leading or among the leaders in benchmarks. In Wikidata query evaluations, Virtuoso exhibited the best overall performance and reliability, outperforming other triple stores on many queries. It uses a vectorized execution engine in C and can push-down SPARQL to low-level SQL-like operations. Virtuoso is especially good at complex join queries and can utilize indexes effectively; many public endpoints (like DBpedia) run on Virtuoso to handle heavy query loads. It scales vertically very well with multi-threading and large memory, so for a single-instance setup on large data.
	2.2 Data ingestion & indexing scalability	2	Efficient bulk loading and indexing, capable of handling very large datasets. Virtuoso provides a bulk loader that can ingest RDF files (Turtle, N-Triples, etc.) at high speed, especially when data is converted to its CSV bulk load format. In the same DBLP test, Virtuoso loaded 390M triples in ~561 seconds (~0.7M triples/sec), producing an index ~13 GB in size (quite space-efficient). It can scale to billions of triples on a single server, and even larger with its clustering (enterprise) edition. While its single-node ingestion rate is excellent, it may require tuning (e.g., adjusting batch sizes, checkpoint intervals).
	2.3 Clustering and distribution model	2	Only with enterprise features. Virtuoso supports two forms of clustering in its commercial editions: replication clustering for high availability, and "elastic" sharding for distributed query. In replication mode, multiple instances maintain copies of the database (master-slave or multi-master), providing failover and load-balancing for read queries. In elastic clustering, Virtuoso can partition the dataset across nodes and parallelize queries. This allows horizontal scaling to very large graphs that exceed a single machine's capacity. These features are not available in the open-source version (which is single-server only), but as an engine capability, Virtuoso has a well-defined clustering solution used in practice.
3. Usability & Deployability	3.1 Ease of deployment and documentation	1	Important effort required to setup. Virtuoso is a mature system but can be slightly complex to set up optimally. On the plus side, it runs on all major platforms and comes with an installer; there's also a Docker image for the open-source edition. Basic installation (starting the server and accessing the SPARQL endpoint) is straightforward. However, to get the best performance, one often must edit configuration.
	3.2 Maturity and ecosystem support	3	Very high maturity. Virtuoso has been in development since the late 1990s and has a strong track record in the Semantic Web community. OpenLink Software continues to maintain it, with the latest stable open-source release (v7.2.14) in late 2024. It's widely adopted - powering central Linked Data services like DBpedia and many Open Data portals. The ecosystem is rich: Virtuoso supports standard APIs (ODBC, JDBC, ADD.NET) for integration, has a SQL interface, and a broad user community.
	3.3 Monitoring and administration tools	3	Strong administrative features built-in. Virtuoso includes the "Conductor" web-based admin console, which allows managing databases, users, and server settings through a GUI. It provides runtime statistics, query execution plans, and the ability to monitor/kill running queries. Virtuoso's server can also expose diagnostic information via SQL system tables and has support for SNMP, making integration with monitoring systems possible. It offers a variety of tooling.
4. Strategic Fit	4.1 Open-source compliance and licensing	2	Partially open-source. Virtuoso's core engine is available as an open-source edition (GPLv2 licensed), which means the source code is accessible and free to use under GPL terms. This edition is feature-rich, but certain enterprise capabilities (notably the cluster scaling and some specific plugins) are only in the proprietary commercial version. It is open in the sense of transparency and community use, but not fully permissive or unified across all features.
	4.2 Long-term sustainability	3	Excellent prospects for long-term support. Virtuoso has been continuously developed for decades and remains central to many projects. OpenLink Software provides commercial support and has a business interest in maintaining Virtuoso. The open-source community also contributes (Virtuoso's GitHub shows ongoing commits). The fact that it's in active use for platforms like Open Knowledge Graphs, and that a new version was released as recently as 2024, indicates ongoing investment.
	4.3 Interoperability and FAIR alignment	3	Very high alignment with FAIR and Linked Open Data principles. Virtuoso was designed with data integration and access in mind, acting not just as a triple store but also as a linked data server. It automatically provides descriptor pages for resources and supports content negotiation to deliver RDF in various serializations or HTML views. This means datasets hosted in Virtuoso can be made accessible via resolvable URIs, directly supporting the "Accessible" and "Interoperable" aspects of FAIR.

Figure 5.10 – Solution C assessment

Virtuoso offers a well-balanced and mature RDF+SQL engine, combining high performance with robust federated querying. Its proven track record in the Semantic Web ecosystem, including powering DBpedia and other major public endpoints, underscores its reliability and scalability. Virtuoso excels at complex joins, scales well vertically, and can ingest RDF data efficiently - though tuning is required for optimal clustering in larger installations.

Its federation capabilities are fully W3C-compliant, and it provides basic reasoning support through rule-based entailment regimes, though not full OWL reasoning. The open-source edition is feature-rich, though advanced clustering capabilities remain commercial-only. Importantly, Virtuoso offers a comprehensive administration interface and monitoring tools, rare among RDF engines.

Deployment can be more complex than lighter alternatives, but Virtuoso compensates with detailed documentation, cross-platform compatibility, and strong community support. From a strategic standpoint, it aligns well with FAIR principles, offering excellent support for data linking and federated access.

Overall, Virtuoso provides the most complete and production-ready foundation among the evaluated options. While some features are gated behind commercial licensing, the open version meets most of GRAPHIA's core needs, especially when paired with optional analytical components like QLever.

5.2.5. Decision

Building on the comparative evaluation (section 5.2.4) and the structured decision-making process led by WP2–T2.1, the GRAPHIA consortium has adopted Virtuoso as the default RDF engine for the platform's core infrastructure. This decision, formalised in ADR002, was validated during the Technical Coordination Board meeting on September 17th, 2025, following extensive discussions and partner contributions.

The decision rests on a combination of strategic, technical, and governance criteria:

- **Functional alignment:** Virtuoso fully supports SPARQL 1.1, named graphs, and update operations - essential capabilities for ontology alignment, semantic annotations, and provenance tracking across WP3–WP5.
- **FAIR and interoperability compliance:** Virtuoso's standards-based architecture (graph-level provenance, RDF-based access control, linked data publishing) ensures alignment with FAIR principles and long-term sustainability.
- **Operational maturity:** Though its setup may be complex, Virtuoso is a robust and production-tested engine with a track record of performance stability in SPARQL-intensive environments.
- **Consortium experience:** Several GRAPHIA partners (OpenCitations, Net7, e-SDF, Foxcub) have prior experience deploying and managing Virtuoso, reducing onboarding time and ensuring smoother support and maintenance.
- **Sustainability and licensing:** The availability of a feature-rich open-source edition (GPL-compatible) enables transparency and avoids vendor lock-in, in line with the project's POSI-aligned governance model.

Category	Criterion	A. GraphDB	B. Qlever	C. Virtuoso
1. Strategic & Ecosystem Alignment	1.1 RDF and SPARQL compliance	3	2	3
	1.2 Reasoning capabilities	3	1	2
	1.3 Federated querying and data linking	3	2	3
2. Technical Feasibility & Sustainability	2.1 Query performance on large datasets	2	3	3
	2.2 Data ingestion & indexing scalability	2	3	2
	2.3 Clustering and distribution model	2	1	2
3. Performance, Operations & Deployment	3.1 Ease of deployment and documentation	2	3	1
	3.2 Maturity and ecosystem support	3	2	3
	3.3 Monitoring and administration tools	2	1	3
4. Strategic fit	4.1 Open-source compliance and licensing	1	3	2
	4.2 Long-term sustainability	3	2	3
	4.3 Interoperability and FAIR alignment	2	2	3
TOTAL		28	25	30

Figure 5.11 – Comparison of evaluations

At the same time, the decision acknowledges that QLever remains of interest due to its excellent query performance on large, static datasets. As such, a feasibility study will be conducted by WP2–T2.2 to evaluate QLever’s potential as a lightweight, read-optimised engine for specific analytical workloads (e.g., batch access, UI endpoints). No dual-engine strategy is currently committed, but flexibility is preserved.

GraphDB, despite its usability and maturity, has been excluded due to its closed-source licensing model and vendor lock-in risks, which conflict with GRAPHIA’s open science and governance requirements.

5.2.6. Architectural implications

The adoption of Virtuoso as the RDF core engine sets a clear foundation for GRAPHIA’s semantic infrastructure. Its integration ensures compatibility with SPARQL-based services, ontology alignment, provenance tracking, and FAIR data publication - all central to the platform’s architecture.

At the same time, the optional evaluation of QLever opens a path towards a dual-engine model. If the feasibility study (WP2–T2.2) demonstrates that QLever can reliably support high-throughput, read-only analytical workloads, particularly in WP5 interfaces or periodic dump-based queries, its role could evolve from experimental to complementary, or even central in specific contexts.

Such a shift would carry significant architectural consequences:

- introducing a decoupled SPARQL endpoint dedicated to large-scale querying,
- reducing pressure on Virtuoso by offloading analytics,
- enabling backend-specific optimizations (e.g. caching, A/B testing, load balancing).

However, this path depends entirely on QLever’s evolution: SPARQL 1.1 completeness, stability under load, and operational integration. The results of the feasibility study will be shared with the Technical Coordination Board between M13 and M18, informing any further architectural adjustment or transition roadmap.

In all scenarios, the architecture remains modular and backend-agnostic: upstream tools (e.g. WebProtégé, metadata harvesters) and downstream services (e.g. discovery interfaces) must not rely on a specific engine’s internals, preserving long-term interoperability and maintainability.

5.2.7. Key considerations

While the chosen architecture offers robustness and flexibility, several points require continued attention to ensure successful implementation:

- **Virtuoso limitations:** the Community Edition provides strong standards compliance but comes with scalability constraints (single-query execution, limited clustering). Workarounds exist, but may require dedicated engineering effort and long-term monitoring. An Enterprise license remains an open question.
- **Operational complexity:** Virtuoso’s setup and debugging can be challenging, especially with outdated documentation and limited community support. Internal tooling and shared expertise, such as OpenCitations Virtuoso

Utilities⁴³ help mitigate these issues. However, onboarding new partners remains resource-intensive due to the specific technical training required to master these operational workflows.

- **Feasibility and scope of QLever:** QLever's future role within GRAPHIA depends on the outcomes of the feasibility study. If the results confirm its performance and integration potential, it could complement Virtuoso in a dual-engine setup - or in some scenarios, take a more central role for analytics. However, governance, maintenance, and compatibility boundaries must remain clearly defined.
- **Consistency with modular principles:** all engine-specific logic must remain encapsulated. Upstream and downstream components must continue to function independently of the RDF backend used.
- **Effort and coordination:** maintaining even a partial dual-engine setup (Virtuoso + QLever or Neo4j) introduces coordination overhead. WP2 must ensure that development and maintenance efforts remain aligned with available resources and cross-WP responsibilities.

5.3. GoTriple KG Technical Architecture

5.3.1. Architectural overview

The technical architecture presented in this section stands as the operational resolution of the requirements and strategic decisions analysed throughout this document. It translates the high-level vision of the SSH Knowledge Graph (SSH KG) as a federation into a concrete deployment model, zooming in on its central component managed by the project: the GoTriple KG. This architecture synthesises the diverse constraints identified in previous chapters: It creates the physical infrastructure capable of supporting the Data Model and Ontology; It acts as the destination for the Data Acquisition Platform; It operationalises the Hybrid Strategy, bridging the authoritative RDF Core with the experimental LPG analytical backend; It

⁴³ A Python-based command-line interface (CLI) developed by OpenCitations to automate complex Virtuoso tasks, such as bulk data loading and index rebuilding. Available at: https://github.com/opencitations/virtuoso_utilities

deploys the selected Technology Stack, establishing Virtuoso as the backbone while evaluating QLever for performance optimization.

Figure 5.12 – Global technical architecture of the SSH Knowledge Graph

As illustrated in Figure 5.12, the resulting structure is organised into five main layers, ensuring a secure data flow from raw sources to end-user services:

- 1. Data Sources** - As described in the Data Model (Section 3.2), this layer aggregates all upstream data providers contributing to the GoTriple KG:
 - harvested metadata from GoTriple repositories and aggregators;
 - datasets generated by WP3 instruments;
 - entities and relationships extracted from text by WP4 AI/NLP modules.
- 2. Data Acquisition Platform (DAP)** - Detailed in Section 4, this central processing hub, the DAP ensures uniform treatment of all incoming data. It integrates services for:
 - Curation and normalisation of metadata, ensuring syntactic and semantic consistency;
 - Enrichment and quality assurance;
 - Orchestration, through an asynchronous event bus implementing an eventual consistency model to avoid blocking dependencies;
 - and Publication, which exports harmonised outputs to both the RDF knowledge graph (Virtuoso) and the GoTriple indexes.

It preserves the RDF-first principle, isolates experimental components (Neo4j, QLever) within well-defined boundaries, and ensures that all ingestion and publication workflows are orchestrated through the DAP - the central, reusable pipeline bridging GoTriple, GRAPHIA, and future data services.

5.3.2. Positioning Neo4j within the GRAPHIA Architecture

While Virtuoso constitutes the authoritative RDF core of the SSH Knowledge Graph, GRAPHIA also explores how Neo4j could complement this backbone, particularly in relation to WP4 analytical workflows and structural exploration tasks.

To clarify the possible roles Neo4j may play, we analysed two complementary dimensions:

1. what portion of the SSH Knowledge Graph (KG) could be made available in Neo4j, and
2. how this data could technically be ingested or synchronised.

These two questions are tightly interdependent. A larger Neo4j dataset requires heavier or more complex ingestion pipelines, whereas selective or task-oriented subsets enable lighter, faster, and more controllable flows.

5.3.2.1. Coverage scenarios: from full replication to targeted subgraphs

The first dimension concerns how much of the KG is projected into Neo4j. The project considered a spectrum of possibilities:

- Full replication, in which Neo4j mirrors all entities, relations, and metadata of the SSH KG;
- Large coherent slices, such as document-citation graphs or author-publication networks;
- Thematic or domain-focused subgraphs, aligned with WP4/WP5 use cases (e.g. citation networks, project graphs, specialised corpora);
- Minimal, ephemeral subsets, created specifically for a computational task and destroyed afterwards.

Scenario	Description	Pros	Cons
Scenario 1.1 - Full graph	Neo4j contains all entities, relations and metadata as in the SSH Knowledge Graph.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maximum completeness • Enables global structural analysis • Allows graph-wide algorithms (centrality, large-scale embeddings) • Closest to the initial proposal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extremely heavy ingestion • Higher resource footprint (RAM, SSD, time) • Complex transformation RDF→LPG • Hard to synchronise when KG grows or evolves
Scenario 1.2 - Large coherent subsets	Neo4j hosts broad functional slices (e.g. documents+citation, authors+relations, entities extracted by WP4, ...).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Covers most analytical needs • Reduces unnecessary volume • More stable and maintainable than full mirroring • Good balance between completeness and efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Still high ingestion volume • Needs explicit definition of the subset boundaries • Some global analyses become impossible
Scenario 1.3 - Thematic / partial subsets	Neo4j contains specialised subgraphs focused on a specific structure or domain. (e.g. citation network, co-author network, entity graph, project graph, domain-specific corpora)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focused, efficient, simple to refresh • Excellent performance for analytics and ML workflows • Minimal resource consumption • Easy to document and reproduce 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited scope • Requires selecting the right subset per use case • Cannot answer cross-domain queries involving the full KG
Scenario 1.4 - Minimal subsets for computation	Neo4j is loaded with just the data required for a one-off analysis or algorithm. (e.g. sampling, local neighbourhoods, task-specific extracts)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very lightweight • Fast to create and destroy • Ideal for ephemeral compute pipelines • No long-term maintenance cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No persistence • Only suitable for local/targeted analyses • Requires reconstruction for every experimental run • Need extra UI, API, background process, user dedicated graph

Our recommendation*

Other option to discuss?

*subject to further evaluation

Figure 5.13 – Comparison of coverage scenarios

Each option offers a different balance between completeness, analytical power, operational effort, and maintenance. Full replication maximises analytical freedom but is technically costly. Selective projections are easier to refresh, document, and govern. Ephemeral subsets minimise long-term cost but require reconstructing data for every experimental run.

To support the exploratory nature of WP4 (AI and structural analysis), Scenario 1.1 (Full replication) is identified as the preferred starting point. Providing the full topology allows for global graph algorithms (e.g., centrality, community detection) that would be impossible on fragmented subsets. However, as noted in the evaluation, this approach has a high resource footprint. Therefore, its implementation remains subject to technical validation: if full replication proves operationally unsustainable, the architecture will fall back to Scenario 1.2 (Large coherent slices).

5.3.2.2. Ingestion scenarios: from direct pipeline output to RDF transformations

The second dimension addresses how Neo4j would be populated. Several ingestion paths were evaluated:

- Direct ingestion from the DAP, producing an LPG-native graph without RDF transformation;
- Batch RDF exports from Virtuoso, allowing perfect semantic alignment but requiring periodic, heavy transformations;

- SPARQL-based projection, exporting specific subgraphs via CONSTRUCT queries;
- Hybrid ingestion, combining continuous DAP flows with periodic semantic updates extracted from Virtuoso (e.g. inferred types or alignments).

Scenario	Description	Pros	Cons
Scenario 2.1 - Direct ingestion from the DAP	Neo4j receives data directly from DAP services (harvesters, enrichment modules, entity extraction). Neo4j becomes another output target, alongside Virtuoso and Elasticsearch.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fast and efficient: no RDF→LPG transformation • Easy to implement in microservice pipelines • Suitable for near-real-time ingestion • Produces a clean, LPG-native graph 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not include RDF reasoning/inferences (if any? And also if inferences are not replicated in DAP) • Requires maintaining two parallel data flows (RDF + LPG) • Higher risk of inconsistencies over time
Scenario 2.2 - RDF export from Virtuoso (batch transformation)	Virtuoso exports RDF snapshots (TTL, NT, RDF-star), which are transformed into LPG via scripts or ETL tools (e.g. SPARQL CONSTRUCT → Neo4j import).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Includes all RDF reasoning and alignment • Data is consistent with the authoritative KG • Reproducible, stable, automated in batch workflows • Works with full graph or subsets • Decoupled from DAP • Easier to fix 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transformation cost can be very high (blank nodes, reification...) • Virtuoso snapshot mechanism needed • Heavy for large graphs • Not suitable for real-time updates • Requires periodic re-import cycles
Scenario 2.3 - SPARQL-based projection (selective extraction)	Specific subgraphs are (regularly?) extracted via SPARQL CONSTRUCT queries and mapped into LPG structures before import.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple and flexible • Perfect for thematic/partial subsets • Minimal volume → fast and resource efficient • Easy to refresh and reproduce 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only captures the selected parts of the graph • Requires careful SPARQL design • Dependent on RDF schema stability
Scenario 2.4 - Hybrid ingestion (DAP + Virtuoso inference-only import)	Neo4j is continuously fed by the DAP (LPG-native entities, extracted metadata, NLP outputs...). In parallel, only the RDF reasoning outputs (alignments, inferred types, schema-driven enrichments) are periodically extracted from Virtuoso and mapped into Neo4j.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DAP = fast + LPG-native, Virtuoso = semantic correctness • Lightweight import from Virtuoso (only inferred triples, not full graph) • Ensures consistency with authoritative RDF reasoning without massive transformations • Real-time(ish) ingestion from DAP with periodic semantic updates • Ideal for graph analytics that still need inferred relations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires maintaining 2 pipelines (DAP stream + Virtuoso inference extracts) • Merging inferred triples into Neo4j may be non-trivial (conflicts, duplicate edges) • Dependent on Virtuoso inference stability and schedule • Works best only if inference volume is predictable/limited

Our recommendation*

Figure 5.14 – Comparison of integration scenarios

Each approach exhibits its own trade-offs in terms of semantic consistency, ingestion cost, operational stability, and update frequency.

Direct ingestion is fast and simple but does not include RDF reasoning unless duplicated upstream. Virtuoso-based extraction ensures semantic correctness but is heavier to operate. Selective SPARQL projections offer flexibility and controlled scope. Hybrid ingestion mixes speed and semantic accuracy, but requires careful coordination to avoid pipeline divergence.

Based on the priority given to semantic integrity and architectural decoupling (see Section 5.1.5), Scenario 2.2 (RDF export from Virtuoso) is identified as the recommended integration strategy. Although it relies on batch processing rather than real-time streams, it ensures that the analytical graph remains a strictly consistent projection of the authoritative RDF core, including all reasoning and inferences, without adding complexity to the DAP ingestion pipelines.

5.3.2.3. Combining the two axes: understanding the design space

Crossing the coverage and ingestion scenarios reveals consistent architectural patterns:

- Full-graph ingestion generally requires RDF snapshot exports (batch transformation), as maintaining an LPG mirror of the entire KG through the DAP would be impractical.
- Large coherent slices align well with SPARQL-based projections or hybrid ingestion strategies.
- Thematic or task-specific subsets naturally pair with lightweight SPARQL extraction or DAP-based LPG ingestion.
- Ephemeral computation subsets rely exclusively on on-demand extraction with no persistent pipeline.

The goal of this exercise is not to pre-select or constrain GRAPHIA to a specific option, nor to position Neo4j as a secondary or optional component.

Instead, the objective is to map the full design space, clarify the technical implications of each path, and ensure that any future decision about Neo4j, whether minimal, extensive, experimental, or strategic—is grounded in a transparent understanding of:

- semantic coherence relative to the RDF core,
- ingestion and maintenance workload,
- performance and scalability requirements,
- integration needs for WP4 (analytics) and WP5 (user-facing services),
- long-term governance and sustainability.

This architectural framing provides the basis for an informed evaluation of Neo4j's role within GRAPHIA and its interaction with the DAP, Virtuoso, QLever, and the global KG workflow.

5.3.3. Estimated size of the GoTriple KG

The estimated size of the GoTriple KG is based on the current scale of GoTriple and on the new categories of metadata introduced through GRAPHIA. Only metadata-level information is considered - no full text, no federated graphs, and no replication of external sources such as OpenCitations or ORKG. These, in case, will be linked via external URIs, not ingested.

The overall volume depends on three main factors:

1. GoTriple's core corpus, including documents, authors, and projects;
2. New source families foreseen in the overall architecture - datasets, media object, and semantic artefacts (e.g. outputs from WP3 instruments);
3. WP4 enrichment services, which will extract entities such as persons, organisations, events, places, cultural objects, and time periods from texts.

The estimated volume of the GoTriple KG reflects both the current GoTriple corpus and the gradual integration of new data sources and enrichment layers introduced by GRAPHIA. These figures are intended solely to inform the technical recommendations and sizing requirements for Virtuoso and QLever. **They do not represent a final or binding projection**, and will be re-evaluated in later development stages as data acquisition pipelines, enrichment coverage, and hosting conditions at PCSS evolve. The sizing aims to remain realistic, balancing expressivity, scalability, and maintainability as the platform matures.

Initial deployment

This first configuration represents the short-term, production-oriented setup. It assumes:

- Use of the current GoTriple corpus (~20 M documents, 18 M authors, 26 K projects);
- Partial author materialisation (about 25 % of profiles with stable identifiers and affiliations);
- Integration of first new sources (\approx 0.5 M datasets, media object, and semantic artefacts);
- Entity extraction coverage on roughly 30 % of documents, with an average of 2 extracted entities per abstract;
- Identifiers (DOI, ISBN, etc.) stored as literals rather than separate nodes;
- Provenance metadata managed via Named Graphs (minimizing impact on node topology).

→ Estimated volume: ~ 40 million nodes and ~ 120 million edges.

This scale allows stable operation within Virtuoso's Community Edition limits, supports realistic ingestion workflows, and avoids unnecessary graph inflation during the early enrichment phase.

Extended configuration (after full integration of sources and enrichments)

This configuration anticipates the graph's growth once new connectors, NLP services, and entity reconciliation pipelines are fully deployed. It assumes:

- Broader author coverage through progressive disambiguation;
- Expansion of new sources (up to 1.5 M additional records from datasets, and media object);
- Wider enrichment coverage (60–80 % of the corpus, with richer event, place, and organisation extraction).

→ Estimated volume: ~ 60 million nodes and ~ 190 million edges.

Rationale and modelling strategy

The estimates are designed to balance semantic richness with operational feasibility. The growth from 40 M → 60 M nodes results mainly from:

- increased author materialisation after reconciliation;
- additional enriched entities extracted from text;
- inclusion of new metadata families (datasets, semantic artefacts).

To keep the graph manageable and semantically coherent, a cautious modelling approach is adopted:

- Identifiers are initially represented as literals, with the option to promote them to nodes only when cross-graph linking becomes necessary;
- Provenance information is expected to be managed through named graphs rather than additional node structures;
- External knowledge graphs are referenced via persistent URIs instead of being replicated locally;
- Inverse relations are introduced selectively, based on demonstrated query or usability needs.

This approach ensures the GoTriple KG remains scalable, FAIR-compliant, and maintainable, with a conservative initial deployment target (~40 M / 120 M) and a controlled growth path toward the extended configuration (~60 M / 190 M) once data pipelines and enrichment services mature.

5.3.4. Requirements for Virtuoso

The deployment of Virtuoso for the SSH Knowledge Graph must ensure reliability, scalability, and maintainability under the expected data volume (40–60 million nodes, corresponding to approximately 200–300 million RDF triples). The following baseline requirements are drawn from Virtuoso’s official documentation^{44 45} and best practices⁴⁶ observed in comparable research infrastructures.

These requirements will serve as a starting point for deployment testing at PCSS and may be refined as the GoTriple KG evolves and performance benchmarks are conducted.

5.3.4.1. Hardware and system environment

- A dedicated server environment is recommended, with at least 32–64 GB RAM and SSD storage to ensure fast read/write access.
- Virtuoso performs best when 60–70 % of system memory is allocated to database buffers, keeping sufficient free memory for the operating system.
- A 64-bit Linux system is preferred for stability and performance.

5.3.4.2. Data storage and indexing

- The default RDF index configuration is suitable for medium-scale graphs such as the GoTriple KG.
- It is advised to maintain the column-store configuration (enabled by default in recent versions) to reduce storage footprint and improve query speed.
- For large deployments, data and log files should be placed on separate disks or storage volumes to improve I/O performance.

⁴⁴ <https://docs.openlinksw.com/virtuoso/rdfperformancetuning>

⁴⁵ <https://vos.openlinksw.com/dataspace/owiki/wiki/VOS/VirtRDFPerformanceTuning>

⁴⁶ https://www.pldn.nl/wiki/Virtuoso_questions

5.3.4.3. Data ingestion

- For initial loading, use bulk-load functions such as TTLP or RDF_LOAD_RDFXML_MT, which support parallel ingestion from RDF dumps.
- When handling large data sets, it is recommended to split RDF files into batches (e.g. 1-2 GB each) and schedule loading during low-traffic periods.
- Re-indexing and checkpoint operations should be executed periodically to maintain performance and data integrity.

5.3.4.4. SPARQL query performance

- Query optimisation is crucial for stability: always restrict the default graph (FROM or FROM NAMED) and avoid unconstrained wildcard queries.
- Complex joins should be monitored with query plans, especially in multi-user environments.
- Public endpoints should apply timeouts and query cost limits to prevent denial-of-service by overly broad queries.

5.3.4.5. Monitoring and maintenance

- Regular maintenance tasks (checkpointing, database compaction, and log cleaning) should be automated.
- Virtuoso's system statistics tables (DB.DBA.SYS_STAT) can be used to monitor cache usage, disk I/O, and buffer efficiency.
- Backups (full and incremental) must be scheduled to protect against data corruption or system failure.

5.3.4.6. Scalability and risk management

- The Community Edition of Virtuoso does not include built-in clustering or high-availability features. Scaling will therefore rely on vertical expansion (RAM, CPU) or read-replica setups for query distribution.
- If future evaluations confirm the benefits of QLever for read-heavy workloads, it may complement Virtuoso by handling analytical queries while Virtuoso remains the authoritative RDF store.

5.3.5. Requirements for Qlever

QLever is currently considered as an experimental analytical backend within GRAPHIA, consistent with the decision framework outlined in Section 5.2.5. Its role is not to replace the RDF core (Virtuoso) but to evaluate alternative query execution models optimised for read-intensive workloads on large, relatively static datasets. The following requirements summarise the minimal setup and considerations for feasibility testing during the first evaluation cycle (M13–M18). They are drawn from QLever’s official documentation⁴⁷ and best practices⁴⁸ observed in comparable research infrastructures.

5.3.5.1. Deployment context

- QLever will be deployed on a separate test environment from the main RDF core, ideally within a containerised or virtualised setup managed by PCSS.
- The goal is to benchmark its query speed, memory footprint, and scalability using representative RDF dumps exported from Virtuoso.
- Only static data snapshots should be used; QLever is not designed for continuous updates or transactional workloads.

5.3.5.2. Hardware and system requirements

- QLever’s performance depends heavily on available RAM. A typical configuration requires 32–64 GB of memory for medium datasets (~100 M triples).
- SSD storage is recommended to handle its custom binary index files, which can reach several hundred GB depending on dataset size.
- As QLever builds a complete index at load time, sufficient temporary disk space (1.5–2× dataset size) must be available during initialisation.

⁴⁷ <https://github.com/ad-freiburg/qlever>

⁴⁸ https://ad-publications.cs.uni-freiburg.de/CIKM_qlever_BB_2017.pdf

5.3.5.3. Data preparation and ingestion

- Data must be provided in N-Triples (.nt) or Turtle (.ttl) format. Each dataset is converted into a compressed index through QLever's build process.
- Indexing is a one-time operation per dataset snapshot and may take several hours, depending on hardware and dataset size.
- Incremental updates are not yet supported; a full re-index is required after each data modification.

5.3.5.4. Query capabilities and integration

- Reflecting its rapid development since our initial evaluation, QLever now implements most of SPARQL 1.1. Support for named graphs, which was absent during the assessment phase, has notably been added, though its efficiency in specific sorting scenarios remains to be validated.
- It provides a RESTful SPARQL endpoint compatible with most RDF clients. Integration with GRAPHIA should therefore rely on API-level decoupling rather than database-level federation.
- Test scenarios should focus on analytical and read-only queries (e.g. exploration, statistics, entity co-occurrence) rather than transactional operations.

5.3.5.5. Evaluation focus

- The feasibility study should assess three main aspects:
 1. Query performance on large, static datasets compared with Virtuoso and established public benchmarks;
 2. Operational complexity (installation, indexing, monitoring);
 3. Potential value for off-loading analytical or high-throughput user interface queries.
- Results of these tests will be presented to the Technical Coordination Board between M13 and M18, to determine whether QLever could be retained as a complementary analytical service.

5.3.5.6. Limitations and risk considerations

- QLever is still under active development and not yet recommended for production use.
- The lack of named-graph support, identified as a blocking factor during the evaluation, has been addressed in the latest versions. However, the recency of this implementation and the ongoing work on update operations currently restrict its use to isolated analytical tasks.
- Index rebuilding after each update can be time-consuming; careful scheduling and version control of datasets are essential.

5.3.6. Requirements for Neo4j

As defined in the architectural decision (Section 5.1.5), Neo4j serves as the dedicated engine for graph analytics and structural exploration within the WP4 experimental module. Unlike the authoritative RDF core, it is not intended for transactional storage but for computational tasks requiring native LPG capabilities (e.g., pathfinding, centrality, embeddings).

5.3.6.1. Deployment and Licensing (Graphs4Good Program)

To support the high-performance requirements of the SSH Knowledge Graph while adhering to its mission of societal impact, GRAPHIA has been accepted into the Neo4j "Graphs4Good" program⁴⁹.

- **Licensing and POSI Alignment:** Through this initiative, the project benefits from the Neo4j Enterprise Edition under a mission-driven license. This aligns with the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI) by leveraging industry partnerships to support non-profit, open scientific research. To ensure long-term reproducibility by the wider community, the data models and queries will remain compatible with the open-source Community Edition.
- **Advanced Capabilities:** Unlike the Community Edition, this license grants access to Causal Clustering and High Availability (HA) features. This allows the analytical module to scale horizontally and ensures resilience, handling

⁴⁹ <https://neo4j.com/graphs4good/>

complex graph algorithms on large SSH datasets without the "single-node" constraints.

5.3.6.2. Hardware and system environment

Graph algorithms are memory-intensive. To support the "Full Replication" or "Large Coherent Slices" scenarios (see Section 5.3.2.1), the following configuration is recommended:

- **Memory (RAM):** A minimum of 64 GB per node is advised. Heap size should be configured to approximately 50% of available RAM, with the remainder dedicated to the page cache for mapping graph files.
- **Storage:** High-performance SSDs (NVMe preferred) are critical for graph traversal performance and import speed.

5.3.6.3. Data Ingestion

With the Enterprise Edition, the platform supports both online incremental updates and high-speed batch loading. However, to maintain semantic consistency with the RDF core (as per Scenario 2.2), ingestion will primarily rely on batch synchronisation using the `neo4j-admin import` tool, while retaining the capability for transactional updates via Cypher if real-time enrichment becomes necessary in later phases.

5.3.7. Operations and security strategy

To ensure the reliability and integrity of the SSH Knowledge Graph, a comprehensive security and monitoring strategy has been defined for implementation across all architectural layers.

5.3.6.1 Authentication and authorization (AAI)

Access control relies on standard protocols:

- **Service-to-Service communication:** Internal microservices within the DAP and interactions with the KG write-endpoints will be secured using API Keys and mTLS (Mutual TLS) where applicable, ensuring that only authorized components can modify the graph.
- **User and admin access:** Administrative interfaces (e.g., for the DAP harvester or Virtuoso maintenance) are planned to be protected via OpenID Connect (OIDC), enabling integration with institutional Identity Providers (IdPs) and ensuring centralized user management.
- **Public access:** Read-only access to the SPARQL endpoint and public APIs will remain open but rate-limited to prevent abuse.

5.3.6.2 Infrastructure security

Hosted at PCSS, the infrastructure will benefit from robust perimeter security, including firewalls and DDoS protection. All data in transit is secured using industry-standard encryption protocols (TLS 1.2 or higher).

5.3.6.3 Monitoring and observability

Operational health will be monitored using industry-standard cloud-native observability tools (such as Prometheus and Grafana), collecting metrics from:

- **Cluster and Infrastructure:** Resource usage (CPU, RAM, Disk) and health status of the underlying OKD/Kubernetes environment and service containers;
- **Application performance:** Query latency, error rates, and ingestion throughput;
- **Service availability:** Up/down status of DAP microservices.

Detailed logs are aggregated to facilitate debugging and auditing, ensuring full traceability of data ingestion and modification events.

6. Implementation roadmap

Development in WP2 will follow an incremental process, based on agile methodologies and continuous integration practices.

The first step is to reuse existing GoTriple content as a data source for the GoTriple KG. This enables the parallel implementation of both the graph and the DAP. To do so, the current GoTriple pipeline (SCRE) can be extended with a new Publisher service that inserts data into the graph(s) by using specific modalities (e.g. SPARQL Update for Virtuoso/qler, or, in case, Cypher for Neo4j), while progressively incorporating new data sources. This allows us to bootstrap the KG using stable and well-understood metadata while validating the basic ingestion mechanisms. This also ensures that enrichment, cleaning and harmonisation workflows contribute directly to the evolving knowledge graph.

At the same time, the design of the DAP will be finalised, with the selection of its software components. Development will start by analysing the potential reuse of the code developed for Matilda, SCRE, and DACE for implementing the DAP services, with particular attention to the Harvester and Publisher as the core components of the platform.

The architecture will then be expanded to include the AI/NLP-based microservices developed in WP4, enabling the extraction of entities, relationships, and semantic annotations from full texts. At this stage, the KG begins to embed not only bibliographic records but also concept-level and semantic information generated by GRAPHIA's intelligent services.

After these extensions have been integrated and validated, we will produce the first complete release of the DAP, supporting all relevant ingestion flows and data types. The DAP will then evolve through successive integrated versions, each extending the supported ingestion flows, data types, and processing capabilities. These iterations will be accompanied by continuous testing and validation activities; in specific phases, automated updates of the front-end systems' content may be temporarily paused to ensure the stability, consistency, and performance of the end-to-end data flows.

As a final outcome, this process will lead to a mature and consolidated version of the DAP, capable of reliably and efficiently updating both front-end systems, while supporting all sources, processes, and enrichments defined in GRAPHIA.

7. Conclusions

This deliverable presents the work done in GRAPHIA tasks T2.2 (*SSH KG Development and Deployment Infrastructure*) and T2.3 (Data Acquisition Platform), whose development started at Month 6. It describes the conclusions drawn by the team at the current stage of work (Month 12), with the majority of the elements already well analysed and specified, but also with some open questions that need to be answered in the following period of the project.

This is specifically related to some technological issues that can only be addressed by performing some extended experiments. Examples of these open points include:

- possible refinements of the TRIPLE Ontology, in particular regarding the management of entities extracted from text, as this will also depend on the actual capabilities of WP4 services that will produce these data
- the choice between Virtuoso and Qlever as the definitive RDF store for the project
- how to organise in practice the coexistence of the RDF and LPG graphs
- the best technologies to be used for implementing the DAP: some examples have been provided here given the experience of the project partners, but during development and operations some different choices may emerge
- the actual size of the GoTriple KG with respect to the estimations presented here
- the infrastructural requirements of the graphs to meet users' demand in the production environment.

In any case, this deliverable represents a sufficient and solid basis to guide development in GRAPHIA over the next phases of the project.